

BETWEEN SECURITY AND HUMANITY: BRITISH NEWSPAPER COVERAGE
OF THE GAZA WAR, 2023–2024

Diana Dikhanbayeva

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Abstract

This dissertation examines the discursive strategies employed by three leading British newspapers – The Guardian, The Telegraph, and The Sun – in their reporting on Hamas and the wider Israel-Palestine conflict between October 2023 and March 2024. Drawing on Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), media framing theory, securitisation theory, and the concept of necropolitics, the study maps how legitimacy, victimhood, and blame were constructed and stratified within mainstream news narratives.

A selected corpus of 75 articles forms the empirical basis, enabling the identification of recurrent linguistic and thematic features across both broadsheet and tabloid traditions. The analysis finds that British coverage largely prioritised Israeli security imperatives and framed Hamas as an unequivocal terrorist actor, while Palestinian suffering was often depersonalised and relegated to the margins. Although differences in editorial line and publication type shaped the presentation of events, several discursive strategies, such as selective grievability, dehumanisation, and asymmetrical sourcing, were evident across outlets.

The findings suggest that British newspaper reporting not only reflected but also reinforced prevailing political discourses, shaping public understandings of legitimacy, violence, and victimhood during the Gaza War. These outcomes advance scholarly understanding of media agency in conflict reporting and highlight the ethical stakes of narrative framing in wartime contexts.

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Abbreviations

BBC – British Broadcasting Corporation

CDA – Critical Discourse Analysis

FBI – Federal Bureau of Investigation

ICC – International Criminal Court

ISIS – Islamic State of Iraq and Syria

ITV – Independent Television (UK broadcaster)

PM – Prime Minister

TV – Television

UK – United Kingdom

UN – United Nations

US – United States

1. Introduction

1.1. *Background*

Media coverage plays a pivotal role in shaping public interpretations of international conflicts, influencing levels of empathy, perceptions of legitimacy, and the scope of policy responses. Reporting on the protracted Israel-Palestine conflict has long been marked by contestation, particularly within the British press, where coverage has often displayed a discernible bias in favour of Israel. Such bias constrains the articulation of Palestinian agency and manifests in uneven terminological choices, most notably, the selective application of the term “terrorism” to acts of violence. These asymmetries in representation carry significant ethical and social implications, as they both distort public discourse and help define the parameters within which policy is formulated.

The confrontation between Israel and Hamas escalated sharply in October 2023, when Hamas launched an unprecedented assault on Israeli territory, prompting intense global media scrutiny. This dissertation examines the portrayal of Hamas and the evolving hostilities in the British press through a critical discourse analysis of three outlets: The Guardian, The Telegraph, and The Sun.

1.2. *Relevance of Research*

The present enquiry is relevant to ongoing debates concerning media framing and the construction of legitimacy during cross-border conflicts. The temporal focus, from 1 October 2023 to 31 March 2024, encompasses decisive moments, ranging from the immediate narrative escalation to the prolonged humanitarian fallout, thereby capturing the dynamic evolution of framing tactics in response to shifting activities on the ground and growing international pressure. Such understanding is indispensable given the media’s capacity to condition public opinion, legitimise policy initiatives, and orient the responses of states and international organisations.

Moreover, this inquiry engages substantively with ongoing discussions regarding ethical journalism, bias in conflict reporting, and the media’s authority to delineate victimhood and legitimacy. By situating these dynamics within the British print press, the dissertation advances both scholarly and practical conversations about the influence exercised by media institutions in shaping representations of conflict.

1.3. *Research Aims and Questions*

This dissertation explores how British newspapers reported on Hamas and the Israel-Palestine conflict between October 2023 and March 2024. The main question of the study is:

How has British print media represented Hamas and the Israel-Palestine conflict in its coverage between October 2023 and March 2024?

Supporting sub-questions:

Q1: How are Hamas and the 2023-24 conflict portrayed in the language and narratives used in British newspapers?

Q2: What recurring themes or frames (e.g. “terrorism,” “self-defence,” “humanitarian crisis”) structure media coverage?

Q3: How do these discourses reflect broader ideological or securitisation narratives?

The questions above deliberately centre on how framing, terminology, and representation are structured within news discourse, shifting analytical focus away from the events themselves. By foregrounding these discursive elements, the study aims to reveal how British print media shapes public understandings of legitimacy, experiences of violence, and the construction of victimhood during the Gaza War.

1.4. Structure of the Dissertation

The dissertation consists of seven chapters. Following the introduction (Chapter 1), Chapter 2 presents a literature review surveying prior scholarship on framing, conflict reporting, and the specific biases that have shaped representations of the Israel-Palestine conflict. Chapter 3 outlines the theoretical foundations of the study, integrating the contributions of CDA, framing theory, securitisation theory, and necropolitics. Chapter 4 sets out the methodological framework, detailing the sampling procedures, analytical methods, and study limitations. Chapter 5 presents the empirical findings, offering a comparative analysis of how each newspaper represented Hamas and the broader conflict through lexical choices, thematic framings, and editorial positioning. Chapter 6 situates these findings within the wider academic discourse, assessing their implications for public understanding and the authority of the media. Finally, Chapter 7 summarises the principal conclusions, highlights the study’s contributions, and proposes directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

The chapter draws on academic literature and credible reports to explore key topics. It first analyses general media coverage of conflicts, focusing on British media's portrayal of wars and violent actors. It then examines the literature on the British media's portrayal of the Israel-Palestine conflict up to 2023, revealing underlying trends and biases. After that, it analyses the UK media's portrayal of Hamas and the Gaza War from October 2023 to March 2024, using contemporary expert analyses. The chapter closes with a review of British media's dissenting and critical coverage, citing alternative voices and debates regarding terminology and balance.

2.1. Western Media Coverage of Conflicts and War Situations

The academic literature shows that news media can shape public perception of warfare and political violence across the globe. In particular, British newspapers have long been recognised as powerful agenda-setters whose framing choices, especially the use of labels such as “terrorist” or “resistance fighter”, have a significant impact on how conflicts and actors are understood (Bhatia, 2005; Entman, 1993).

A consistent finding across research is that British and wider Western media tend to apply these terms selectively, according to political context and existing alliances. Non-state groups opposing the West are often branded as terrorists. In contrast, similar violence perpetrated by allies or Western militaries is described in neutral or even euphemistic terms (Kumar, 2015; The New Humanitarian, 2023). The phrase “one person’s terrorist is another’s freedom fighter” highlights the contestable and subjective nature of such narratives (Bhatia, 2005). For instance, British media coverage of the war in Ukraine continuously regarded Ukrainian fighters as “defenders” or “resistance”, thereby legitimising violence against an occupying power (The New Humanitarian, 2023). However, as several authors remark, armed Palestinian groups confronting Israeli occupation do not receive similar terminology; instead, they are typically labelled as “terrorists” (The New Humanitarian, 2023; Philo and Berry, 2011).

Linguistic choices are not trivial as they can shape empathy and moral judgment. Research in “peace journalism” notes that mainstream reporting in the UK often adopts a “war journalism” approach: coverage is event-driven, elite-focused, and dichotomous, with little context for root causes (Galtung, 2002; Lynch and McGoldrick, 2005). This is evident in the reporting of civilian casualties – the emotionally loaded terms like “massacre”, “atrocious”, or “slaughter” are the default framework when framing Western or allied victims, whereas passive framing dominates the narrative for non-Western contexts (Butler, 2009; The New Humanitarian, 2023). For example, the phrase “Israelis were killed” is commonly used, while “Palestinians died” is often employed in a way that removes agency and downplays questions of responsibility (The New Humanitarian, 2023).

Research on the British media system reveals a predominant reliance on official governmental and military views (Philo and Berry, 2011). “Indexing” tends to stifle critical or dissenting voices, resulting in news stories that reflect the confines of mainstream political discourse (Herman and Chomsky, 1988). The BBC, for instance, avoids the term “terrorist” unless quoted.

This practice illustrates the controversies and contradictions that can emerge from media language (Simpson, 2023).

The theoretical literature highlights how these patterns are underpinned by media framing and critical discourse strategies (Entman, 1993; van Dijk, 1998). Entman's framing theory explains how news discourses select specific facets of reality, making them more perceptually prominent to favour particular interpretations (Entman, 1993). While the media may highlight topics deemed worthy of public attention (agenda-setting), they simultaneously shape the evaluative lens through which those topics are interpreted (Weaver, 2007; McCombs and Ghanem, 1997). Van Dijk argues that journalistic discourse reinforces entrenched ideological biases: it tends to frame "us" actions positively while portraying "them" through negative prisms, often downplaying or omitting counter-evidence. He terms this the ideological square, a dynamic that reveals how differential salience is assigned to in-group versus out-group narratives (van Dijk, 1998). These practices ultimately consolidate dominant Western or allied perspectives, systematically marginalising opposing views (van Dijk, 1998; Wodak, 2015). Securitisation theory further claims that categorising certain actors as "threats" or "terrorists" enables the justification of exceptional state responses, which shape public perception and legitimise military action (Jackson, 2005).

The New Humanitarian (2023), Philo and Berry (2011), and Sirhan (2021) reviews emphasise the British media's legitimisation of violence perpetrated by states and their allies while casting non-state or oppositional violence as illegitimate. This systemic bias shapes the British media's approach to Middle Eastern conflicts, highlighting the need for a more nuanced and critical analysis of how Palestinians and Hamas are represented. Recognising this bias not only provides a conceptual foundation for the present study, but also reinforces its focus on the discursive construction of legitimacy and illegitimacy in news coverage.

2.2. British Media Coverage of the Israel–Palestine Conflict (Pre-2023)

Existing research shows that British media coverage of the Israel-Palestine conflict has for a long time been dominated by bias, especially in the use of narratives that frame the story from an Israeli perspective, sidelining Palestinian narratives. This situation has been documented in television, broadsheets, and tabloids and has lasted over the last twenty years (Philo and Berry, 2011; Sirhan, 2021).

Philo and Berry (2004; 2011) in their works "Bad News from Israel" and "More Bad News from Israel" revealed a lack of ITV and BBC contextual reporting on the Palestinian occupation and the refugee crisis. They discovered that TV news programme audiences did not comprehend who the occupier was in a given context (Philo and Berry, 2011). Survey results appearing alongside the content analysis indicated that many British viewers were misinformed, with some assuming that Israel was the occupied region. The analysed language appeared to follow a pattern in which Israeli officials framed the situation – Israeli actions were termed defensive, while Palestinian actions were portrayed as aggressive.

The BBC's commitment to "balance" was described as problematic, as its pursuit of neutrality often led to false equivalence – giving equal weight or airtime to fundamentally unequal or

asymmetric positions (Philo and Berry, 2011). For instance, reports of Palestinian casualties resulting from Israeli military action, especially during the conflicts of 2008, 2009, 2012, and 2014, as well as in more recent ones, were almost immediately followed by statements from Israeli officials justifying such actions or shifting focus to Hamas activities, thereby minimising the acknowledgement of Palestinian suffering.

Recent findings confirm that these trends persist within print media. Sirhan's (2021) study of the top five British newspapers, *The Guardian*, *The Independent*, *The Times*, *The Daily Mail*, and *The Telegraph*, revealed notable linguistic asymmetries. She highlighted how Palestinian violence towards Israelis was often described using active verbs with specific attribution ("Palestinian gunman kills Israeli"). In contrast, Israeli violence towards Palestinians was reported in a passive voice ("Palestinians were killed") devoid of any clear subject. This created a narrative where Palestinians were portrayed as aggressive actors and Israelis as either victims or defensive actors (Sirhan, 2021).

Sirhan's work also addresses the concepts of occupation and international law. References to the illegal occupation of the West Bank and Gaza were rare, and when present, they were often marginalised or overshadowed by more dominant storylines. Terms such as "disputed territories" or "security barrier" were frequently used in place of more accurate legal terms like "occupied territories" or "apartheid wall" (Sirhan, 2021; Shupak, 2022). Similarly, Israeli settlements were hardly ever labelled as illegal under international law; instead, they were advanced as part of ambiguous territorial disputes, thus masking the power imbalance and violations inherent in the described situation.

An imbalance in sourcing emerged as another notable finding. Israeli officials were quoted far more frequently than Palestinians (Sirhan, 2021). This inequality is not only a result of the selective decisions made by editors but also because of underlying conditions. Several foreign journalists stationed in the region are based in Israel and fluent in Hebrew, whereas far fewer work in the Palestinian territories or speak Arabic. This spatial and linguistic bias contributes to the predominance of Israeli perspectives and the underrepresentation of Palestinian voices (Sirhan, 2021).

Even outlets more sympathetic to Palestinian issues, such as *The Guardian* or *The Independent*, were shown to reproduce dominant frames. Sirhan (2021) pointed out that those papers were more likely to mention the occupation or the humanitarian aspects of Israeli actions but relied heavily on Israeli official sources, often framing narratives around Israeli concerns. Detailed accounts of Israeli security incidents or Hamas rocket fire preceded references to Palestinian casualties, which rendered the Palestinians' suffering in a reactive framework.

Public and institutional pressures also shape media output. *The Guardian's* own readers' editor acknowledged receiving regular complaints from both pro-Israel and pro-Palestinian readers but noted that pro-Israel complaints were often more organised and persistent (Elliott, 2016). The newspaper faced pressure over headlines that appeared to present Palestinian victims too prominently, leading to editorial caution. Similar dynamics were observed at the BBC, which faced criticism from all sides for its terminology and framing (Simpson, 2023).

Furthermore, efforts by Israeli state agencies and lobbying groups to influence international media coverage, sometimes referred to as “hasbara”, were also well documented (Sirhan, 2021). These campaigns aimed to portray Israel’s military actions as self-defensive measures while delegitimising Palestinian resistance as terrorism. Some scholars argue that, in addition to provoking strong public reactions and media controversies, such advocacy can contribute to a climate of editorial caution within UK newsrooms (Sirhan, 2021).

The lack of contextual depth within British media coverage has further contributed to the lack of historical and legal framing in British narratives. Scholars argue that the media portrayal of Palestinians as “violent” actors obscures the underlying political issues and overlooks critical factors such as the blockade of Gaza, settlement expansion, and the denial of statehood (Philo and Berry, 2011; Shupak, 2022). This reductionist framing facilitates the depiction of groups like Hamas not as political or ideological actors engaged in a broader struggle, but simply as terrorist entities, stripped of context and complexity.

To conclude, prior to 2023, the literature analysing British coverage of the Israel–Palestine conflict consistently highlighted several key imbalances: an Israeli-centric framing, coupled with an overemphasis on Israeli security; an imbalance in the representation that sidelined Palestinian voices; a deafening silence on legal or historical context. Understanding such patterns is essential to grasp how British newspapers framed Hamas during the ongoing Gaza War communicating mainstream narratives of terrorism, self-defence, and occupation. Our focus will be the period October 2023- March 2024.

2.3. British Media Coverage of Hamas and the Gaza War (Oct 2023 – Mar 2024)

Hamas’ attack on Israel in October 2023 and the war in Gaza triggered a significant shift in the British media narrative of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. While research on this period is still emerging, early studies provide valuable insights into how British newspapers reported on Hamas, Israel, and the whole conflict.

A major study by the Centre for Media Monitoring (CfMM, Hanif, 2024) analysed over 25,000 articles from leading UK news sites and hundreds of hours of broadcast coverage during the first months of the war. The CfMM found a systematic bias favouring the Israeli narrative. For instance, more than 50% of authors used the term “Israel-Hamas war”, thus using the Israeli narrative and diminishing the Gaza assault’s scope. Strong language, including “massacre”, “atrocities”, and “barbaric”, was descriptive in nature of Hamas’s violence towards Israelis. At the same time, Israeli military actions in Gaza that had led to the deaths of Palestinians were described using less vigorous language and in a passive voice. Israelis were depicted as victims eleven times more often than Palestinians in the news, and statements justifying Israel’s right to self-defence vastly outnumbered any mention of Palestinian rights or resistance (Hanif, 2024; Yusuf, 2024).

Another finding was the disparity in sourcing: Israeli officials and perspectives were quoted three times more often than Palestinian ones in TV coverage. In the very first weeks of the war, foreign journalists were barred from entering Gaza, leading to a significant limitation in accessing Palestinian viewpoints. Yet, UK media outlets rarely made efforts to seek alternative

Palestinian voices to fill this gap. As a result, the overall narrative remained heavily dominated and shaped by the Israeli perspective (Harb, 2024).

Similar trends were found in the content analysis of right-wing newspapers – The Times, The Telegraph, The Daily Mail, and The Sun (Shehadi et al., 2024). These papers used graphic and emotive language in 44% of headlines about Israeli victims but in only 7.5% of headlines about Palestinian victims (Shehadi et al., 2024). Moreover, the number of words used to describe the suffering of Israelis was over ten times more than those used for the suffering of Palestinians. In addition, many Israeli official statements, such as accusations on Hamas’s use of hospitals, were covered without scrutiny, even when they later faced doubt or contradiction. In contrast, reports of Palestinian suffering or allegations against Israel were frequently caveated with scepticism or presented as claims by Hamas rather than established facts.

The tendency to adopt Israeli viewpoints was not limited to right-wing or tabloid outlets. An analysis by Talaat et al. (2024) of The Guardian, The Independent, and The Mirror showed similar, if less pronounced, patterns. These papers gave much greater attention to Israeli hostages than to Palestinian prisoners, and even when reporting on Palestinian deaths, they were more likely to use neutral or passive constructions. For instance, in the coverage of the Al-Ahli Hospital bombing, UK media outlets placed more emphasis on the Israeli officials’ doubts and denials than on the immediate suffering of Palestinian civilians. Historically, media coverage had more frequently attributed violence to Hamas than to Israel, reinforcing the portrayal of Hamas as the primary aggressor (Talaat et al., 2024).

Some outlets, especially The Guardian, did include more humanitarian reporting and provided a limited platform for Palestinian voices, as in the case of publishing a “Gaza diary” account by a Palestinian citizen. Regardless, in such instances, the overall framing was still dominated by concerns for Israeli security. At the same time, Hamas was only referred to as a terrorist group with scant mention of the occupation, blockade, or international law (Talaat et al., 2024).

The literature also highlights the amplification of unverified or later discredited claims that supported Israeli narratives. Notably, the allegation that Hamas fighters had beheaded Israeli children was widely circulated in UK newspaper headlines despite lacking verification. Such reports played a key role in framing Hamas and Palestinians as barbaric, thereby influencing public sympathy and shaping the discourse (Shehadi et al., 2024). In contrast, claims of Israeli atrocities or violations of international law received less prominent coverage and were more likely to be presented as disputed or omitted from headlines altogether (Hanif, 2024).

Another key aspect was the internal debate within media organisations. More than one hundred journalists from the BBC, along with public figures, signed open letters condemning themselves for “dehumanising Palestinians” and not granting proper agency for the deaths of civilians in Gaza (Stavrou, 2024). These acts of self-reflection show how the “balance” and the reluctance to assign clear responsibility can serve to reinforce dominant narratives. Despite the BBC’s long-standing editorial guidelines discouraging the use of the term “terrorist” in its own voice, Simpson (2023) argues that the organisation’s framing of Hamas and selective fact presentation ultimately reflected the prevailing attitudes of both the government and the broader public.

Civil society and advocacy groups sought to influence media coverage by focusing on historical context and international law. However, they struggled to shift the dominant discourse, which continued to centre on Israeli victimhood and the narrative of threat by Hamas (Caabu, 2023).

In conclusion, the literature and expert analyses indicate that British newspaper coverage of the Gaza war in 2023-2024 largely adhered to established patterns: Hamas was portrayed as a terrorist group; Israeli military actions were framed as contextually defensive; and Palestinian suffering was either downplayed or presented in less humanising terms.

For all their attempts to diversify and enrich their narratives, outlets could not escape the dominant framing. These patterns illustrate the enduring presence of selective compassion, asymmetries within the sourcing, and the primary influence of the political backdrop within framing the news around the Israel-Palestine conflict.

2.4. Alternative and Critical Narratives in British Media

Unlike most British newspapers, which echoed official positions during the 2023 Gaza War, some alternative and critical perspectives were present, albeit to a limited extent. Columnists, independent media outlets, civil society organisations, and advocacy groups attempted to counter dominant narratives by introducing humanitarian and legal framings, aiming to broaden the public discourse and challenge prevailing portrayals.

With a particular focus on Arab-British relationships, advocacy groups like Caabu have long expressed frustration with media narratives that neglect fundamental issues like collective punishment, the blockade of Gaza, and war crimes (Caabu, 2023). Their efforts have centred on urging journalists to incorporate international law and highlight the humanitarian crisis caused by the occupation, while calling for less reliance on official Israeli narratives.

Middle East Eye, The New Arab, and Novara Media, being part of alternative and left-leaning media, provided more detailed and critical reporting that prominently featured Palestinian voices and legal framings. They incorporated powerful terms such as “collective punishment”, “siege”, and “apartheid” that were rarely used in mainstream media (Shehadi et al., 2024). In doing so, they offered a consistent platform for Palestinian perspectives and legal analysis, which stood in stark contrast to the institutionalised narratives of national newspapers.

Mainstream commentators like Owen Jones and Peter Osborne also drew attention to selective empathy in the reporting of Israeli and Palestinian suffering. Their critique suggested a need to shift from accepting Israeli state statements at face value towards recognising Palestinian claims and casualties.

2.5. Conclusion

The scholarly literature indicates that British reporting on the Israel–Palestine conflict continues to favour Israeli viewpoints and official communications, marginalising Palestinian narratives and omitting crucial historical and legal frames (Philo and Berry, 2011; Sirhan, 2021; CfMM and Hanif, 2024). After October 2023, the imbalance deepened: British outlets categorised Hamas as a terrorist entity, employed charged language to convey Israeli losses,

yet described Palestinian casualties in abstract, depersonalised terms (CfMM and Hanif, 2024; Shehadi, Mustafa and Omer, 2024).

Such unequal representation illustrates a necropolitical ordering in which Palestinian mortality becomes both less visible and less grieved in dominant discourses (Mbembe, 2003; Butler, 2009). Alternative angles circulated by advocacy organisations and independent journalists, although proactive, failed to penetrate public perception substantively because primary public discussion remained dominated by selectively edited newspaper accounts and authoritative pronouncements.

The literature, therefore, surfaces a decisive scholarly gap: an absence of comprehensive studies tracing how media framing and lexicon produce legitimacy and influence understandings of warfare and violence. This dissertation aims to respond to that gap via a rigorous integration of critical discourse analysis and framing approach.

3. Methodology

3.1. Methodological Approach

The analysis adopts a qualitative approach, grounded in Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) as its governing conceptual and methodological framework (Fairclough, 1995; Richardson, 2007; van Dijk, 1998). CDA is regarded for its capacity to expose the often-overlooked intersections of language, power, and ideology in media texts. In examining state violence, particularly within the Israel-Palestine conflict, CDA enables a layered interrogation of lexical choices, grammatical structures, framing strategies, and source selection. These choices collectively confer legitimacy on some actors, marginalise others, and shape public understanding of complex, conflictual events (Wodak and Meyer, 2016; Philo and Berry, 2011).

The research is situated within Fairclough's three-dimensional framework for CDA, which analyses discourse on three interrelated levels:

1. Textual analysis examines lexical choices, agency construction through active/passive voice, identity terminology (e.g., "terrorist," "militant," "victim"), and the use of evaluative or emotive language.
2. Discursive practice focuses on the life cycle of the articles, considering the identities of quoted sources, the genre of the piece (e.g., news report, editorial), and how these factors shape meaning and reception.
3. Social practice places the discourse within broader institutional, political, and societal contexts, interrogating how themes such as national security, counter-terrorism, historical memory, and international law inform British media coverage (Fairclough, 2013).

This framework is further enriched by van Dijk's (1998) socio-cognitive model and Wodak's Discourse-Historical Approach (2001), which introduce additional analytical categories including actor nomination, predicate attribution, and structures of argumentative justification. The integration of these approaches yields a methodologically robust framework for analysing newspaper texts.

The study also incorporates media framing theory (Entman, 1993), which clarifies how news texts select and organise information to construct particular realities, as well as securitisation theory (Buzan et al., 1998; Balzacq et al., 2016), which explores how media framing of threats can legitimise extraordinary policy responses. Together, these frameworks illuminate how the press circulates enduring frames, constructs dominant narratives, and embeds them within broader ideological formations, thereby enabling a nuanced and critical analysis of discourse.

3.2. Data Selection and Sampling

A purposive sample of 75 articles was drawn from three prominent British newspapers: The Guardian (centre-left broadsheet), The Telegraph (centre-right broadsheet), and The Sun (tabloid/populist), each representing a distinct editorial tradition and readership (Philo and Berry, 2011; Richardson, 2007). The selection captures a spectrum of ideological perspectives and rhetorical styles, enabling both cross-sectional and comparative analysis.

A coherent and transparent sampling procedure was applied:

1. The coverage period, October 2023 to March 2024, was deliberately chosen to capture the immediate aftermath of the 7 October attacks and the subsequent evolution of media narratives.
2. Database searches used keywords such as “ Hamas,” “ Gaza,” “ Israel,” “ October 7,” “ war,” “ hostages,” and “ airstrikes.” Inclusion criteria mandated (a) publication within the defined timeframe; (b) a primary focus on Hamas or the Israel-Palestine conflict; and (c) authorship by a staff journalist, excluding brief reports and syndicated wire content.
3. From each outlet, 25 articles were selected, ensuring a balanced distribution of formats (news reports, features, and editorials) and coverage of key thematic episodes in the conflict.

Each article was catalogued in a comprehensive summary table (see Appendix 1), detailing title, date, length, section, synopsis, key thematic frames, and rationale for inclusion. This level of documentation ensures transparency, facilitates triangulation, and supports systematic comparison of textual content and editorial positioning across outlets.

With 75 articles, the dataset is sufficiently large to allow for thematic saturation, detailed textual analysis, and meaningful comparative insights over time and across publications (Silverman, 2020). While not statistically representative of the entire British print media landscape, the sample is purposefully curated to be information-rich, capturing dominant and recurring discursive patterns relevant to the study’s main questions (Philo and Berry, 2011; Richardson, 2007).

3.3. Coding and Analytical Grid

At the core of the analysis lies a custom coding and analytical grid, designed to operationalise categories from CDA and guide the interpretation of each article (see Appendix 2). Drawing on foundational work in critical media studies (Philo & Berry, 2011; van Dijk, 1998; Entman, 1993), the grid integrates both predefined and emergent codes, including:

1. Actor Portrayal

Terminological choices used to describe individuals and groups (e.g., “terrorists,” “fighters,” “civilians”), including the use of scare quotes or euphemistic language, signal how actors are categorised and positioned within the narrative.

2. Key Terms and Labels

Evaluative vocabulary applied to actors (e.g., “barbaric,” “innocent,” “aggressive”) reveals underlying biases. The choice of syntactic structures determines whether actors are rendered accountable or indistinctive (e.g., “ Hamas killed civilians” vs “ Civilians died in Gaza”). This shows how judgement is assigned and how agency is constructed.

3. Agency and Voice

Identifying whose voices are foregrounded, Israeli officials, Palestinian civilians, humanitarian actors, and whose perspectives are marginalised or omitted altogether.

4. Frame

Recognising recurrent thematic filters such as securitisation, humanitarian crisis, resistance, legitimacy, self-defence, and the ethics of warfare, along with subtler discursive patterns that shape the narrative.

5. Emotive and Rhetorical Language

The use of figurative language, emotionally charged claims, evaluative statements, and rhetorical techniques that either inflame or dampen audience sentiment.

Systematic coding proceeded iteratively: initial deductive categories, derived from theoretical frameworks and prior literature, were refined through inductive engagement with the data. Coding decisions were documented within the analytical grid and cross-referenced with the article summary table, enabling intertextual comparison and supporting robust, evidence-based conclusions.

3.4. Data Analysis Procedure

The analysis advanced through three interlinked phases:

1. Close Reading and Coding

A methodical, line-by-line reading of each article was conducted, with relevant themes and categories marked according to the analytical grid. This process surfaced recurring linguistic patterns, framing techniques, and inconsistencies in source attribution, facilitating the trace of emergent discursive regularities and exceptions.

2. Comparative and Thematic Analysis

Coded data were then subjected to intra- and inter-publication comparison. This facilitated the identification of convergent and divergent portrayals, shifts in topical emphasis, as well as underlying rhetorical strategies. Mapping these patterns was essential for understanding how different editorial orientations recontextualised similar events and actors.

3. Reflexivity and Validation

A reflexive stance was maintained throughout the process. All coding and interpretative decisions were evaluated against existing scholarship, and regular feedback was sought from the academic supervisor to mitigate researcher bias and strengthen the credibility of the findings (Silverman, 2020).

Throughout the analysis, illustrative extracts, paraphrased segments, and grouped thematic clusters were well-documented, ensuring that all claims were grounded in textual evidence. Deviant and contradictory cases were also preserved to avoid analytical oversimplification and to present a balanced depiction of the discursive landscape within the sample.

3.5. Limitations

All methodological designs are subject to limitations, and this research is no exception. Even a carefully constructed framework must contend with potential blind spots and biases.

First, subjectivity is inherent to Critical Discourse Analysis. The interpretive nature of CDA means that the researcher's prior experiences, assumptions, and positionalities inevitably influence analytical decisions (Richardson 2007). While efforts were made to enhance rigour through transparent procedures, systematic coding, and ongoing supervisory feedback, some level of subjectivity is unavoidable.

Second, the study's findings are case-specific and may not be generalisable to all British media or other periods of conflict. The analysis is limited to four major newspapers and a six-month timeframe (October 2023-March 2024), which, while broad for a qualitative study, cannot account for all perspectives, media types, or future developments (Silverman, 2020). Similarly, the exclusive focus on print media does not capture the dynamics of television, radio, or social media coverage, which may differ in framing and impact.

Third, although a relatively large sample of 75 articles was analysed, the purposive sampling means the results reflect information-rich and prominent cases rather than a statistically representative cross-section of all coverage (Silverman, 2020). Some relevant perspectives, such as those in regional or alternative outlets, may be underrepresented.

Recognising these limitations enhances the transparency and methodological integrity of the study. Despite its constraints, the research offers a critical lens through which to examine how British newspapers constructed narratives around Hamas and the broader Israel-Palestine conflict.

3.6. *Ethical Considerations*

Although this study relies exclusively on newspaper archives and does not involve any human participants, ethical considerations remained an essential component of the research design.

The Israel-Palestine conflict is a highly sensitive and polarising subject, and careless treatment risks reinforcing rather than critically examining prevailing narratives. Any language deemed inflammatory or dehumanising was included solely in the context of quotation and excluded from the researcher's own narrative framing (Philo and Berry, 2011). References to violence, grief, and competing political actors were presented in a neutral and measured tone to ensure that analysis, rather than provocation, remained the primary objective.

The study also deliberately separated its critique of media discourse from any judgement of identifiable individuals or communities. This distinction helped preserve analytical distance and avoided moralising interpretations, focusing instead on recurring patterns of portrayal (Richardson 2007).

Transparency in sourcing and methodological openness were maintained throughout. All primary and secondary sources were systematically logged, and the inherent limitations and subjectivities of qualitative research were acknowledged (Silverman 2020).

Ultimately, the study seeks to contribute meaningfully to academic literature and shape public discourse on how media depict conflict, with a commitment to accuracy, responsibility, and respect for the subjects involved (Richardson 2007).

3.7. *Researcher's Positionality*

In qualitative study, the researcher's positionality plays a critical role in shaping both the design and interpretation of the study (Silverman 2020). The author of this dissertation is a UK-based postgraduate student in media and communication, with an academic interest in conflict coverage and media bias. While the researcher holds no personal or political affiliation with either side of the Israel-Palestine conflict, it is acknowledged that all forms of interpretive analysis are shaped, consciously or otherwise, by one's background, values, and experiences (Richardson, 2007).

By explicitly acknowledging these influences, the study invites readers to critically assess the interpretive lens through which the findings are presented. Such reflexive transparency is intended to enhance the study's credibility, in line with the epistemological stance of Critical Discourse Analysis, which rejects the ideal of complete neutrality and instead foregrounds positional awareness as a strength (Richardson 2007; Silverman 2020).

3.8. *Conclusion*

This chapter has outlined the research questions and methodological framework guiding this dissertation. Using Critical Discourse Analysis, the study applies a structured, multi-level approach to British print media coverage of Hamas and the Israel-Palestine conflict.

A purposive sample of 75 articles from three major UK newspapers enables comparative analysis of discursive patterns and editorial emphases. Ethical considerations, study limitations, and researcher positionality have also been addressed to ensure research transparency.

The next chapter sets out the theoretical foundations before presenting the empirical findings.

4. Theoretical Framework

This chapter outlines the conceptual and theoretical foundations that underpin the analysis, focusing on how British newspapers construct public discourse around war, violence, and the legitimacy of military action. While the study is rooted in CDA, the interpretive emphasis is placed on media framing theory, securitisation theory, and necropolitics.

4.1. *Framing Theory*

Framing theory, introduced by Goffman (1974) and later adapted for media studies by Entman (1993), holds that journalists construct narratives by selectively emphasising certain aspects of reality while marginalising others. This process shapes public perception by directing attention, assigning responsibility, and promoting specific courses of action (Entman, 1993).

In the context of armed conflict, recurrent frames are often identifiable. For example, the “terrorism” frame foregrounds threat and culpability, whereas the “humanitarian crisis” frame highlights civilian suffering and appeals for empathy (Entman, 1993; Philo and Berry, 2011). Journalists construct these frames through lexical choices, headline construction, source selection and positioning, and the strategic inclusion or omission of contextual information (Butler, 2009). The portrayal of Hamas’s attacks as “Israel’s 9/11” invokes a familiar security narrative likely to resonate with pre-existing audience beliefs (Shehadi et al., 2024).

Unlike agenda-setting, which concerns what issues are brought to public attention, framing focuses on how those issues are presented or interpreted (McCombs and Shaw, 1972; Entman, 2007). During the 2023 Gaza War, British newspapers mobilised competing frames: some prioritised Israeli military security and sovereignty, while others highlighted civilian suffering and breaches of international law (Hanif, 2024; Talaat et al., 2024). These framing choices shape how readers interpret both events and actors.

The dissertation applies framing theory to identify and analyse dominant interpretive structures within British print media. It explores how journalists and editors confer legitimacy upon particular claims and actors, thereby influencing audience perceptions of the conflict (Entman, 1993; Philo and Berry, 2011).

4.2. *Securitisation Theory*

Securitisation theory examines how certain issues are discursively constructed as security threats requiring exceptional measures beyond the scope of normal political procedures (Wæver, 1995; Buzan et al., 1998). At its core lies the idea that security is performative: when an authoritative actor labels a phenomenon as an existential threat, this speech act legitimises responses that would otherwise fall outside established or legal norms.

The securitising actor, typically a political or institutional authority, deploys strategic narratives to portray a situation, group, or event as posing immediate danger to valued referent objects, such as the state, public order, or national identity (Buzan et al., 1998). This logic is evident in portrayals of Hamas as an “existential threat to Israel” or in its alignment with ISIS. If the audience accepts this framing, it authorises a range of extraordinary measures, from military action to emergency legislation, that are shielded from standard political contestation.

For this dissertation, securitisation theory provides a productive analytical lens through which to examine the construction of threat and the discursive mechanisms that confer legitimacy on exceptional responses. Integrated with CDA, it enables a systematic interrogation of how public narratives around the conflict are constructed, revealing whether media discourse merely mirrors official rhetoric or introduces alternative framings that disrupt the dominant securitising logic (Buzan et al., 1998).

4.3. Necropolitics

Necropolitics, first articulated by Mbembe (2003), enlarges the inquiry into media representation to ethical and philosophical dimensions by interrogating the power to proclaim the worth of lives and the permissibility of their abandonment. It thus supplements Foucault's biopolitical framework, articulating the capacity to will death as decisively as the capacity to cultivate life (Mbembe, 2003).

In situations of armed conflict and military governance, Israel and Palestine being a primary case, necropolitics reveals how governmental and military sovereignty designates entire populations as vulnerable or, more plainly, as disposable. The media's representational strategies are not ancillary; they elevate some fatalities to the order of public significance while diminishing or anonymising others (Butler, 2009). Butler's concept of "ungrievable lives" surfaces alongside this inquiry, signalling how certain groups, often cast as antagonists or intruders, are rendered immune to the full acknowledgement of death as a human irremediable loss within collective memory and justice discourse (Butler, 2009).

This framework directs analytical attention to tropes that strip subjects of human specificity: the recurrent invocation of the term "militant" in the absence of identificatory detail, or the neutralising qualifier "collateral damage" applied to civilian fatalities, both of which work to displace moral accountability. Simultaneously, narratives that cast mass death as an unavoidable sacrifice for security function to sanctify the primal ethical equivalence of one group's survival against the expendability of another.

Incorporating necropolitical thought expands the methodological palette, compelling a scrutiny that outstrips the identification of frames or threats and engages the latent value hierarchies orienting audience judgment regarding war, violence, and the constitution of legitimacy (Mbembe, 2003; Butler, 2009).

4.4. Conclusion

The research adopts an integrated framework combining CDA, framing theory, securitisation theory, and necropolitics. CDA provides the core methodological basis, enabling examination of texts at the micro (linguistic), meso (discursive practice), and macro (sociopolitical) levels (Fairclough, 1995). Framing theory enables the categorisation of dominant narratives, such as "terrorism" and "humanitarian crisis" (Entman, 1993). Securitisation theory further explains how existential threats are constructed and legitimised through language (Buzan et al., 1998; Wæver, 1995), while necropolitics interrogates the ethical implications and the differential valuation of human life in war media coverage (Mbembe, 2003; Butler, 2009).

Together, they allow for a multi-layered analysis of British press reporting on Hamas and the Gaza War, moving fluidly between linguistic detail (CDA), narrative construction (framing), political performance (securitisation), and moral representation (necropolitics).

5. Findings and Analysis

This chapter critically examines the discursive constructions, narrative strategies, and framing practices employed by three prominent British newspapers – The Guardian, The Telegraph, and The Sun – in their coverage of the Israel-Gaza conflict from October 2023 to March 2024. Drawing on CDA, framing theory, and other relevant scholars and papers (van Dijk, 1998; Fairclough, 1995; Wodak, 2015; Entman, 1993; Buzan et al., 1998; Butler, 2009; Mbembe, 2003), this analysis identifies how each outlet constructed legitimacy, blame, victimhood, and humanitarianism in the context of the conflict using language and representation. Each of the newspapers, liberal (The Guardian), conservative (The Telegraph), and populist/tabloid (The Sun), exhibited distinct editorial identities that shaped both the thematic selection and event interpretation. The chapter discusses the evolution of these discourses throughout the conflict while considering the implications of media representation, public perception, and power relations.

5.1. *The Guardian*

The Guardian's initial coverage foregrounded the shock of Hamas's attack on October 7, 2023, adopting a securitised and "war on terror" frame that legitimised Israeli retaliation (Buzan et al., 1998). Headlines such as "Israel and Hamas at war after surprise attacks from Gaza Strip" (October 7, 2023) established a macrostructure of conflict and causally linked hostilities to Hamas's actions, normalising Israeli emergency measures (McKernan, 2023). The reporting amplified Israeli leaders' rhetoric: for instance, Prime Minister Netanyahu's declaration, "We are in a war and we will win it," was presented as a classic securitising speech act, defining the crisis as existential and urgent (McKernan, 2023). The reporting constructed an ideological binary, with Hamas labelled as "militant group," "fighters," and "terrorist organisation," while Israeli actions were described with institutional legitimacy ("responded," "mobilised"), thereby reinforcing a legitimacy gap (van Dijk, 1998; Wodak, 2015). Early articles frequently dehumanised Hamas as barbaric "butchers" while individualising Israeli victims as innocent, reflecting van Dijk's assertion that out-group violence is emphasised and in-group suffering humanised (McKernan, 2023).

The visual discourse further reinforced these frames: images of Israeli cities ablaze and civilians under attack were foregrounded. At the same time, Palestinian casualties were reported as aggregate "collateral damage" in "retaliatory Israeli airstrikes" (McKernan, 2023). Thus, Palestinian suffering was rendered less "grievable" (Butler, 2009), supporting a hierarchy of visibility and empathy. The narrative privileged Israeli security concerns and moral legitimacy in the initial weeks of reporting.

Nevertheless, The Guardian's initial coverage of the conflict predominantly adopted a securitisation and victim-centric frame. Sherwood's (2023) article, "How the Hamas attack on the Supernova festival in Israel unfolded," relied heavily on survivor testimonies, relatives' accounts, and emergency responders to construct a highly emotionally charged narrative. The language foregrounded Israeli innocence and the horror of the assault, employing phrases such as "unprovoked attack on civilians" and reinforcing a terror-oriented frame. In contrast, Palestinian casualties were mentioned only briefly and statistically, implicitly establishing a hierarchy of grievability (Butler, 2009).

As the conflict escalated, The Guardian's framing shifted toward the humanitarian crisis and the proportionality of Israel's response. Carroll's (2023) report, "Dozens killed after Israeli airstrikes on Gaza refugee camp," signalled a discursive turn, presenting Israeli military

justifications alongside Palestinian accusations of a “heinous massacre” and collective punishment. It reflected growing international concern, citing “mounting international alarm” and describing conditions in Gaza as “catastrophic.” By incorporating statements from international organisations, UN officials, and human rights groups, the report situated the events within broader debates on international law and ethical accountability. This approach aligns with Wodak’s (2001) discourse-historical method and Fairclough’s (1995) notion of intertextuality, embedding multiple perspectives and expanding the discursive field beyond national or securitised framings.

This shift is also visible in headlines, which increasingly foregrounded the scale of civilian suffering (“More than 900 dead in Gaza since Saturday as shelling hits school, hospitals and homes”, October 10, 2023) (Michaelson, 2023). Palestinian civilian voices and international criticism were legitimised alongside continued Israeli justifications, reflecting an evolving “ideological square” (van Dijk, 1998). The Guardian gradually shifted from a securitisation-led narrative, instead foregrounding humanitarian and legal issues. It was marked by language highlighting “escalating civilian casualties” and “dire humanitarian conditions,” as well as emotionally resonant accounts of entire families killed and “no safe place” in Gaza (Carroll, 2023; Michaelson, 2023).

By late 2023 and early 2024, The Guardian’s discourse had become increasingly integrated with humanitarian law and legal accountability. The live blog “US risks’ complicity in war crimes” (December 9, 2023) and similar reports foregrounded accusations against both Israel and its allies, presenting a contest between state security narratives and human-rights perspectives (Ratcliffe et al., 2023). Reporting on international diplomatic pressure, the use of terms such as “war crimes,” “siege,” and “collective punishment,” and the explicit naming of Palestinian victims signalled a significant reframing. This shift enabled the inclusion of multiple voices and perspectives, humanitarian, legal, and international, alongside state security justifications. Consequently, the conflict was reframed not solely as a security issue, but as a broader normative debate (Fairclough, 1995).

As of March 2024, legal discourse had become central to The Guardian’s reporting (“Starvation in Gaza likely key to UK legal advice on war crimes,” March 30, 2024) (Graham-Harrison, 2024), which accused Israel of strategic war crimes and analysed the conflict through the lens of international ethics and law.

Thus, The Guardian’s editorial voice shifted from rationalising Israel’s security concerns to foregrounding humanitarian and legal critiques. CDA (van Dijk, 1998; Wodak, 2015; Fairclough, 1995), as well as media framing theory (Entman, 1993), illustrated how The Guardian constructed and adjusted a narrative that responded to changing events, on-the-ground dynamics, and public and institutional sentiment, reflecting evolving discourse throughout the conflict.

5.2. The Telegraph

The Telegraph’s coverage of the Israel-Gaza conflict was characterised by a strongly securitised and militaristic discourse, consistently aligning with the official Israeli narrative, particularly in the early stages. The paper’s immediate response to the October 7 attack, as reflected in headlines such as “ Hamas terrorists butcher civilians as stunned Israel suffers ‘9/11’ moment” (Rothwell and Vasilyeva, 2023), framed the events as an absolute atrocity, drawing explicit analogies with Western traumas such as the 9/11 attacks. This invocation of global terror tropes not only universalised Israeli victimhood but also positioned the conflict

within a familiar “war on terror” paradigm (Wodak, 2015; van Dijk, 1998). Hamas was consistently labelled as “terrorists” and “gunmen”, with predication strategies emphasising “butchery” and “slaughter”, while Israeli victims were personal, named, and emotionally individualized (Rothwell and Vasilyeva, 2023; Oliphant, 2023a; Oliphant, 2023b).

The Telegraph’s use of elitist sources, including Israeli officials, Western leaders, and military spokespeople, helped to legitimate its dominant frames and reinforce a binary of civilisation versus barbarism. Entman’s (1993) framing functions were fully enacted: the problem was defined as an unprecedented act of terror, the causal interpretation rested solely with Hamas, moral evaluation positioned Hamas as “absolute evil”, and the recommended treatment was robust, even exceptional, Israeli retaliation. Graphic and emotive language, such as references to “children shot in their beds”, heightened this moral outrage and normalised military escalation as justified and necessary.

As the conflict progressed, The Telegraph continued to privilege Israeli military agency and the narrative of moral urgency. Reports such as “Israel pounds Gaza with one of the heaviest ever missile assaults ahead of ground invasion” (Oliphant, 2023a) highlighted the magnitude of Israel’s response, framing it within the logic of necessary retaliation. Palestinian suffering, while acknowledged, was frequently positioned as an unfortunate but inevitable byproduct of a legitimate war. This structural privileging of Israeli agency, evident through narrative sequencing and the prioritisation of Israeli quotes and explanations, indicates van Dijk’s (1998) notion of agency allocation in media discourse.

A key feature of The Telegraph’s approach was its reliance on historical analogies and atrocity rhetoric to strengthen its stance. The coverage of the Kfar Aza kibbutz massacre, notably through stories such as “Hamas slaughtered babies and children in Kfar Aza kibbutz massacre” (Oliphant, 2023b), invoked Holocaust and ISIS analogies to maximise the moral contrast. Through Wodak’s discourse-historical approach, the reporting activated collective memory and historical trauma, cementing a dichotomy between Israeli civilisation and Hamas barbarity. The intense focus on atrocity, amplified by unverified but highly emotive details, served to create a discursive hierarchy of grief (van Dijk, 1998), wherein Israeli losses were foregrounded as uniquely tragic and grievable.

The Telegraph introduced more strategic and geopolitical analysis as the conflict shifted into a longer campaign. The “Six scenarios for the endgame of Israel’s invasion of Gaza” (Rothwell and Shamalakh, 2023) typified this development, mapping future outcomes but always within a securitised frame. The language continued to describe Hamas as a “terrorist organisation” and to privilege the Israeli “right to defend” as the central premise. While ethical concerns, such as the risk of “a second Nakba” or “ethnic cleansing”, were briefly engaged, they were treated as hypothetical or extreme, not as central narrative challenges. Humanitarian frames were acknowledged, but usually as subordinate or contextually necessary, not as drivers of the story.

From November 2023, some Telegraph articles began referencing international criticism of Israel, but largely to dismiss or counter it rather than scrutinise Israeli actions. Pieces such as “Hamas, not Israel, is perpetrating ‘collective punishment’ in Gaza” (Taub, 2023) employed counter-framing strategies that shifted blame onto Hamas, portraying it as responsible for Palestinian suffering by using civilians as human shields and manipulating humanitarian narratives. The reporting deployed argumentation strategies (Wodak, 2015), emphasising the threat posed by Hamas to justify Israeli actions. International organisations and human rights

groups were portrayed as misinformed or manipulated, further entrenching the legitimacy of the Israeli securitisation narrative.

Entering 2024, The Telegraph's news coverage increasingly reported the humanitarian disaster in Gaza. Reports like "Rising hunger in Gaza turning children into skeletons" (Sebouai and Cullinan, 2024) highlighted the suffering and malnutrition that civilians in Gaza endure. However, these pieces still framed the suffering as the consequence of prolonged warfare, blockades, and scant aid, with blame shared among multiple actors. Even as the humanitarian frame gained salience, it rarely displaced the primary security narrative, and Israeli strategic imperatives remained central.

A further point of divergence with The Guardian emerged in The Telegraph's coverage of international legal action. Articles such as "The International Court of Justice has been weaponised against the Jewish state" (Hausdorff, 2024) framed legal proceedings as politically motivated attacks on Israel, presenting them as a new front in the ongoing war. The legal aspect was therefore incorporated within the boundaries of the securitisation concept and framed as an Israeli legitimacy vulnerability rather than a means of enforcing humanitarian responsibility.

In conclusion, The Telegraph's coverage from October 2023 to March 2024 focused primarily on narratives of securitisation, outrage, and justification of Israeli military action. Although there was an increasing visibility of humanitarian concerns toward the later stages of the conflict, such issues were framed as tragic yet inevitable byproducts of war, reinforcing the logic of relentless military action. The paper's Hamas-centred language was harsh, emotive, and highly evaluative. Israeli operations, by contrast, were discussed in a matter-of-fact or even reverential tone, largely devoid of critical judgment. Over time, the coverage adapted more nuanced strategic and legal analyses but remained fundamentally anchored in the logic of security and existential threat. CDA demonstrates that the dominant discourses – terror, heroic retaliation, and political defence – persisted, recalibrated as necessary to reinforce the outlet's overarching narrative stance.

5.3. *The Sun*

As a popular tabloid, the Sun approached the Israel-Gaza conflict with overt sensationalism and emotive framing. It used shocking headlines, oversimplified dichotomies, and hero-villain pairings alongside personalisation. Within this narrative, the paper was the most openly dehumanising towards Hamas and the most vocally supporting Israeli retaliation, while also including sentimental narrative strategies involving British or Western individuals.

From the outset, The Sun adopted a register of shock, vengeance, and hyperbole. The front-page report "Netanyahu vows to reduce Gaza to 'rubble' as he blitzes Hamas in revenge for terror bloodbath dubbed 'Israel's 9/11'" (Rogers and Hooper, 2023) encapsulated the themes of revenge, militarism, and Western trauma. The language and imagery, such as "blitzes Hamas", "reduce to rubble", and 9/11 analogies, established a clear frame of justified retribution and existential threat (Buzan et al., 1998). In terms of nomination and predication (Wodak, 2015), Hamas was systematically constructed as "terror monsters", "savages", or "evil", while Israeli actors were cast as righteous or heroic. Palestinian suffering was minimised or presented as background statistics, with little narrative complexity or direct focus.

Human-interest stories formed a central pillar of The Sun's coverage, often personalising the tragedy through British or Western victims. The report "Chilling last message from missing Brit Jake Marlowe after Hamas gunmen 'kill 260' and send hundreds fleeing at festival"

(Hooper and Goodwin, 2023) exemplified the tabloid's localisation of horror and grief. The Sun constructed "grievability" (Butler, 2009) by leveraging emotional proximity and detailed storytelling, centring on individual trauma, especially that of a relatable or British figure. The suffering of Palestinians was largely absent or noted only statistically, underscoring a systematic exclusion of the "other's" narrative (Mbembe, 2003; van Dijk, 1998).

As the conflict continued, The Sun's discourse intensified its demonisation of Hamas, frequently using sensational and graphic language. Headlines such as "How evil Hamas commanders are training boy soldiers to battle Israeli forces" (Parker and Hamilton, 2023) foregrounded the "evil" of Hamas, deploying Wodak's nomination strategy of demonisation. This narrative strategy reinforced the justification for Israeli military actions, framing Hamas as not only an existential threat to Israel but also as victimisers of their own people (for example, by "indoctrinating children" and using civilians as shields). Shocking details, such as body-cam videos and emotionally laden descriptions of 'atrocities', supported the tabloid's goal of outraging readers and validating brutal retaliatory measures. Depictions of Palestinian children featured them solely as pawns of Hamas's schemes rather than casualties of Israeli action.

The portrayal of Israeli victims in narratives, as well as the stories of hostages and diasporas, served to evoke empathy. For example, "Chilling last message from missing Brit Jake Marlowe after Hamas gunmen 'kill 260' and send hundreds fleeing at festival" (Hooper and Goodwin, 2023) and "Ten charity workers among hundreds held by Hamas terrorists – with nine volunteers murdered by savages" (Parker and Kaniuk, 2023) focused on British and Israeli families affected by violence and hostage-taking. Empathy was mobilised in the service of reinforcing support for Israeli retaliation, with little or no suggestion that humanitarian compromise was viable or desirable.

The Sun's approach to visuals was consistent with its textual strategies. For instance, articles such as "Netanyahu vows to reduce Gaza to 'rubble'..." (Rogers and Hooper, 2023) and "How evil Hamas commanders 'are training boy soldiers to battle Israeli forces preparing to storm Gaza'" (Parker & Hamilton, 2023), were paired with harrowing images, including burned-out buildings, grieving families, and militarised Israeli forces, while images of Hamas fighters were rendered sinister and anonymous, reinforcing an explicit us-versus-them dichotomy (Kress and van Leeuwen, 2001).

During moments of international mediation, such as the late-November ceasefire and hostage exchange, The Sun's narrative briefly incorporated humanitarian and hope-inflected themes. The reports like "First Israeli hostages set to be freed in HOURS as four-day ceasefire begins after nearly 50 days of fighting" (Braddick, 2023) brought in optimism but were always undercut with scepticism. These moments of optimism were quickly eclipsed by dominant narratives framing the conflict as a war that must continue until Hamas is defeated. Coverage rapidly reverted to reinforcing the legitimacy of sustained Israeli military action, portraying it as both necessary and justified.

By the end of the period (early 2024), The Sun's coverage remained steadfast in its demonisation of Hamas and justification of Israeli military operations. Articles such as "Israel on high alert for 'revenge attacks'..." (English, 2024), "Israeli student 'alive' 100 days after she was seen begging 'don't kill me'..." (Hussey, 2024), and "'Gaza's Bin Laden' Yahya Sinwar is filmed fleeing in terror tunnel..." (Allhusen, 2024) reinforced themes of existential threat, demonisation, and the justification of Israeli military action.

In summary, The Sun's dominant discourses – the terror/evil frame, the revenge/justice frame, and a humanitarian victim frame – were selectively applied to Israelis, British nationals, and allies. The paper's framing was highly consistent: the conflict was a melodrama of good versus evil, in which good must prevail through overwhelming force. Nuance, complexity, and Palestinian civilian narratives were systematically excluded. Securitisation theory (Buzan et al., 1998), CDA (van Dijk, Wodak, Fairclough), and framing theory (Entman, 1993) illuminate how The Sun's reporting simplified and polarised the conflict, mobilising emotional engagement and populist support for the ongoing war.

5.4. Conclusion

This chapter has examined how British newspapers framed the Israel-Gaza conflict, demonstrating how coverage was shaped by editorial ideology and genre (Philo & Berry, 2011; Hanif, 2024). Securitisation and threat construction were prominent in early reporting, while humanitarian and legal frames gained traction in liberal-oriented outlets but remained secondary in conservative and tabloid media (CfMM & Hanif, 2024).

Through CDA, informed by van Dijk (1998), Wodak (2015), and Fairclough (1995), alongside framing theory (Entman, 1993), the analysis reveals the enduring influence of securitisation discourse, the selective extension of grievability, and the persistence of editorial frames despite evolving contexts. These patterns shape public perception, influence legitimacy, and determine whose voices are heard during crises (Butler, 2009; Mbembe, 2003).

The following chapter will interpret these findings within broader academic debates and consider their implications for media power and the framing of international crises.

6. Discussion

This chapter provides a comparative discussion of the main findings, synthesising the discursive tendencies across *The Guardian*, *The Telegraph*, and *The Sun* in their coverage of the Israel-Gaza conflict from October 2023 to March 2024. Despite observable editorial divergences, shared discourse patterns emerged, shaped by the conflict's dynamics and the ideological stance of each outlet. The discourses reflected distinct editorial and ideological standpoints, exhibiting varying degrees of evolution across the three outlets over time.

6.1. Overview of Each Newspaper's Coverage

The *Guardian* consistently adopted a multi-perspective approach, juxtaposing critical analysis with factual reportage, integrating humanitarian and legal frames alongside security logic. Notably, while the paper foregrounded the horror of the October 7 attacks, it consistently granted discursive space to humanitarian consequences in Gaza, frequently referencing international law and human rights. Its language remained measured, featuring diverse voices and a liberal editorial ethos oriented towards challenging official narratives and foregrounding marginalised experiences (Philo, 2012).

By contrast, the *Telegraph* delivered coverage firmly rooted in securitisation, closely aligned with official Israeli and broader Western governmental discourses. Hamas was constructed as an existential terror threat, and Israel's military response was legitimised through a narrative of national self-defence. The broadsheet reported military strategy, security competence, and the logic of deterrence, with only occasional and carefully framed criticism of Israeli actions, typically labelled as questions of tactical rather than ethical concerns (Freedman, 2017).

The *Sun*, operating from a populist tabloid paradigm, employed an emotionally charged and binary narrative. The conflict was routinely cast in 'good versus evil' terms, with Israeli retaliation valorised and any support for Palestinians either minimised or problematised. The *Sun's* language was marked by sensationalism, overt appeals for vengeance, and the routine conflation of Palestinian civilians with enemy combatants, thus simplifying complex realities in favour of a mobilisation logic (Richardson and Stanyer, 2011).

6.2. Securitisation and Threat Construction

Securitisation was a dominant discursive frame across all outlets in the immediate aftermath of October 7, with each newspaper constructing Hamas's attack as an existential threat to Israel and, by extension, to Western values more broadly (Buzan et al., 1998). However, the modalities of this securitisation and its intersection with other frames varied considerably.

The *Guardian* initially reported the Hamas attacks as a profound security crisis but approached securitising rhetoric with analytical scepticism. Netanyahu's speech acts were contextualised, and the consequences of total war were problematised through frequent references to proportionality and humanitarian risk. Over time, The *Guardian* decentred securitisation by reframing the humanitarian situation in Gaza as a pressing security threat for civilians, thus both challenging and extending the boundaries of the security frame itself.

The *Telegraph* advanced a far less critical version of securitisation. The headlines evoked historical trauma ("Israel's 9/11"), while Hamas was firmly positioned as an unequivocal and savage villain. The scrutiny directed at Israeli military actions seldom questioned their legitimacy; instead, it focused on how well they achieved the stated operational objectives.

Even limited critiques, such as those regarding strategic foresight, were contained within a securitised rationale, reinforcing the dominant narrative of existential threat as an editorial priority.

The Sun offered a maximalist rendering of securitisation, combining militaristic rhetoric with explicit calls for vengeance and routine use of dehumanising tropes. Securitisation extended beyond the conflict itself to encompass domestic British contexts, with support for Palestinians framed as a threat to public order. Thus, the Sun legitimated extraordinary violence and policed the boundaries of national solidarity through its coverage.

Comparatively, while all three outlets converged on securitisation in the immediate term, clear divergences soon emerged. The Guardian's coverage evolved towards a critical engagement with security narratives, integrating humanitarian and legal concerns. The Telegraph maintained a security-first paradigm, insulated mainly from critical humanitarian challenges. The Sun persisted with populist securitisation, constructing an unambiguous "enemy other" at home and abroad.

6.3. Humanitarianism and International Law Frames

Throughout the conflict, there was also an attempt to incorporate a humanitarian dimension centred on civilian suffering, international law, and moral accountability, which served as a counterweight to the other dominant narratives within the security paradigm in the coverage provided by the British press. However, this frame's development and relative prominence were inextricably linked to each publication's editorial policy and ethical stance.

The Guardian demonstrated early and proactive integration of humanitarian themes. As early as mid-October, the newspaper's reportage incorporated references to "collective punishment" and invoked international legal norms, with headlines and columns foregrounding the scale of the humanitarian crisis in Gaza. Through the use of statements from UN officials, human rights activists, and medical personnel, The Guardian shifted away from the singular focus on the security frame's violence-centric perspective. This shift became more evident as casualties mounted, with critical reports given prominence and commentary questioning the legality of Israeli operations. Following the late November ceasefire, Guardian editorials displayed a clear stance advocating for the prevention of violence while invoking the equal worth of all human life, regardless of nationality. Thus, the paper attempted to portray the conflict as a dual narrative where Anglophone states privileged security, while non-Western actors demanded adherence to humanitarian law and moral intervention.

The Telegraph, by contrast, acknowledged the humanitarian dimension mainly as an ancillary or secondary concern. In its initial coverage, civilian suffering was framed as an inevitable consequence of retribution – Palestinian suffering described as unfortunate but necessary collateral damage in pursuit of Israel's military objectives. When humanitarian issues surfaced during broadcasts of people being displaced or of crises in hospitals in Gaza, they were often overshadowed by concerns for Israeli security or attributed to the actions or constructs of Hamas (e.g., "human shields"). Allegations of war crimes or "collective punishment" were either ignored or accompanied by Israeli counterarguments. While The Telegraph did not ignore humanitarian realities, its framing consistently privileged the security imperative and the legitimacy of state action, with humanitarian costs framed as tragic byproducts rather than as causes for substantive moral critique (Freedman, 2017).

The Sun offered the least engagement with the humanitarian frame, particularly regarding Palestinian suffering. Where present, its humanitarian focus centred almost exclusively on Israeli victims and hostages, whose accounts were laden with emotive detail and personalisation. The framing of reports on humanitarian pauses or aid convoy transits focused on the need to release hostages rather than acknowledging the need to relieve civilian suffering. Criticism of Israel was minimised; the suffering of Gazan civilians was dismissed as Hamas propaganda. Therefore, humanitarianism did not function for The Sun as an independent frame that could challenge the security narrative; instead, it acted as a mechanism for perpetuating the innocence-versus-villainy dichotomy that characterised the tabloid's editorial line.

To sum up, The Guardian became the foremost advocate of the frames of humanitarianism and international law, placing civilian protection and legal responsibility at the core of its storyline as the conflict progressed. The Telegraph partly acknowledged and wrote about humanitarian concerns but always filtered them through concepts of security and state legitimacy, relegating them to a secondary position. Humanitarianism was mainly ignored or dismissed by The Sun if it clashed with preferred moral binaries. These differences reflect not only journalistic priorities, but also the ideological fault lines shaping British media coverage of war and crisis.

6.4. Grievability and Necropolitics: Whose Lives Are Counted?

A central ethical and discursive fault line in British press coverage of the Israel-Gaza conflict concerned the question of grievability, namely, whose lives were rendered mournable and whose deaths were backgrounded or anonymised (Butler, 2009). Closely associated with this is the necropolitical dimension defined by Mbembe (2003), where socio-political frameworks delineate which populations are rendered killable or erased from the public sphere. All three newspapers exhibited marked asymmetries in constructing grievable life, though with varying degrees of reflexivity and hierarchy.

The Guardian distinguished itself by progressively increasing its coverage of Palestinian civilian suffering, particularly as the conflict's toll on human life became apparent. While initial reporting mirrored much of the British press in foregrounding Israeli casualties, both individualised and contextualised, later reporting shifted to feature comprehensive accounts of Gaza's destruction, including testimonies from aid workers and families, as well as statements from international agencies. Most notably, The Guardian acknowledged the scale of loss on both sides. It also engaged with the unequal recognition of loss by highlighting these disparities and publishing opinion pieces informed by Butler's critique of grievability (Butler, 2009). While limited in scope, this editorial self-reflection signalled a willingness to interrogate its own representational imbalances and invited readers to consider the moral implications of such coverage.

The Telegraph maintained a pronounced hierarchy of grievability throughout the period under review. The deaths of Israelis, mainly from Hamas's initial attacks, received detailed coverage with emotional language and intense, sustained narrative focus, including civilian victims. By contrast, the deaths of Palestinians, particularly those caused by Israeli military operations, were typically reported as abstract metrics. When Palestinian suffering received more attention, it was framed either as regrettable but necessary or as the fallout of Hamas policies, such as the use of "human shields." This structuring of grievability, whereby Israeli loss was rendered viscerally and Palestinian suffering only abstractly, reinforced both the legitimacy of Israeli military conduct and the broader security framing of the conflict.

The Sun represented the most extreme iteration of grievability asymmetry. Israeli and Western victims were consistently individualised and humanised through personal stories, photographs, and emotive appeals to readers. Conversely, Palestinian victims were rarely humanised; their deaths were rendered as numerical appendages to reports on Israeli military action or omitted entirely except when necessary to contextualise a specific narrative (e.g., during hostage exchanges). The Sun's approach went further, actively devaluing and at times dehumanising Palestinian life, collapsing civilian suffering into a homogenised enemy image. By consistently foregrounding the victimhood of "our side" and obscuring or demeaning the losses of the "other", The Sun constructed a stark moral universe in which only certain lives were deemed worthy of public mourning (Richardson and Stanyer, 2011).

All three newspapers exhibited a distinct disparity regarding the narrative valuation of mortality, where Israeli lives received disproportionately greater attention and ethical significance than Palestinian lives. The Guardian, initially complicit in this imbalance, later demonstrated more reflexivity, seeking to represent Gazan suffering and address the politics of grievability. The Telegraph maintained a restrained but rigid hierarchy, while The Sun instituted a near-total erasure of Palestinian loss. Such patterns raise serious ethical concerns because the media largely shaped public empathy, marginalised humanitarian critique, and normalised civilian suffering through selective framing of whose lives count.

6.5. Dehumanisation and Demonisation

The use of dehumanising language and the demonisation of adversaries were another salient discursive practice observed across the British press. Dehumanisation functions to justify violence by framing the enemy as subhuman, whereas demonisation positions them as an existential danger to a moral social order (Khosravini, 2015).

While reporting the news, The Guardian avoided the use of dehumanising terms such as "terrorist" or "barbaric" and instead quoted Israeli officials or survivors of violence. While the absolute violence of Hamas was condemned, the newspaper also highlighted the dangers of adopting dehumanising rhetoric, warning against the corrosive impact such language has on hopes for resolution and mutual recognition. As such, The Guardian demonstrated greater self-awareness.

The Telegraph, while maintaining a formal register, employed hardline terminology that contributed to the demonisation of Hamas. Fighters were described as "terrorists," and terms like "slaughter" or "butchery" were commonplace, with frequent analogies to historical villains such as ISIS and Nazis. Even when these phrases were quoted, the surrounding context made it difficult to portray the Palestinian side empathetically. In coverage of the conflict's later stages, Palestinians in Gaza were often depicted as passive victims of Hamas or as part of a faceless, suffering mass, erasing agency and reinforcing a simplified moral binary.

The Sun embraced dehumanising and demonising tropes to the greatest extent, deploying an arsenal of pejoratives like "monsters", "inhuman", "savages" and consistently collapsing the distinction between Hamas fighters and the wider Palestinian population. Notably, The Sun extended this logic to domestic actors, branding pro-Palestinian protesters in the UK as "traitorous" or complicit with "evil". This construction of the conflict as a battle of civilisation against inhumanity, both at home and abroad, left almost no space for alternative readings or empathetic engagement.

The discourse of dehumanisation and demonisation was widespread and consistent but differed in tone and levels of self-awareness. The Guardian practised restraint and reflexivity, while The Telegraph employed dehumanisation in a broadsheet style. The Sun engaged in rhetorical overindulgence, contributing to the rigid consolidation of in-group/out-group divisions. These linguistic practices had the same effect: denying the possibility of mutual recognition, legitimising extreme violence in international and domestic contexts, and deepening polarisation.

6.6. Inclusion and Exclusion of Voices

The question of who can shape narratives within media offers a different prism of divergence for the three newspapers. The scope of coverage that includes multiple voices played a critical role in defining the framing of the conflict and the legitimacy of claims.

The Guardian stood out with its pluralistic inclusion of voices. Its coverage often included Israeli and Palestinian officials, international organisations, NGOs, and advocacy groups. More notably, The Guardian did not exclude ordinary Palestinians, Gaza's medical staff, humanitarian workers, and critics of both Hamas and Israeli policy. This approach gave rise to a dialogic, polyphonic narrative structure that enabled the representation of conflict, contestation, and debate (Philo, 2012).

The Telegraph implemented a selective inclusion of voices, prioritising official and establishment figures. The dominant speakers in the narrative included Israeli officials, Western political leaders, and military experts, while Palestinian civilians' voices were largely omitted and instead represented through mediated summaries. International humanitarian figures sometimes featured, but their contributions were framed as mere background information or countered by Israeli responses. The net effect was to narrow the narrative space to those aligned with state or expert authority, consistent with The Telegraph's conservative editorial ethos.

The Sun provided a highly filtered selection of voices, amplifying only those that reinforced its pro-Israel, pro-military, and emotive stance. Foregrounded were Israeli leaders and victims, while Western political endorsement of Israeli policies was heavily emphasised. Palestinian voices, especially those expressing civilian pain or demanding restraint, were nearly entirely absent. Domestic dissidents and pro-Palestinian protesters were cast in a negative light, and their presence served to uphold the paper's moral bias.

Inclusion and exclusion of voices not only reflected but also actively reinforced the ideological priorities of each outlet. The Guardian employed a multi-vocal approach, facilitating complexity and empathy; in contrast, The Telegraph and The Sun favoured sympathetic and supportive sources and excluded dissenting or adversarial perspectives. The outcome was the creation of strikingly different communicative universes for each newspaper's audience, resulting in diverse understandings within the public sphere and shaping the possibility of policy contestation.

6.7. Editorial Orientations and the Evolution of Media Discourse

The ideological frameworks guiding each newspaper fundamentally shaped the British press's approach to the Israel-Gaza conflict between October 2023 and March 2024. Each publication's editorial line determined the frames and narratives that were constructed.

Drawing on Fairclough's (1995) three-dimensional model – text, discursive practice, and social practice – these differences become especially clear. The Guardian, focused on liberal internationalism, aligned with an emphasis on human rights, international law, and the humanitarian toll of warfare. At the level of discursive practice (Fairclough, 1995), this came through in the paper's shift from initial securitisation and event-centred headlines to coverage that increasingly foregrounded humanitarian consequences and legal debates. For example, while The Guardian acknowledged Israeli suffering in the early days of the conflict, by the end of October, headline coverage was devoted to the UN's warnings regarding a "humanitarian catastrophe" and legal discourses of "collective punishment" were prominently featured. The Guardian consistently presented a range of voices, including those of humanitarian workers, Palestinian family members, and human rights advocates, thereby pluralising the national narrative and exemplifying discursive practice pluralism (Fairclough, 1995). As previously noted, The Guardian also engaged in reflexive self-criticism, publishing several opinion pieces that addressed the anonymisation of Palestinian deaths in British media and challenged dominant frameworks of grievability (Butler, 2009).

In contrast, The Telegraph maintained a strong securitised narrative throughout the examined period. At the level of discursive practice, it closely aligned with Israeli and broader Western perspectives (Fairclough, 1995), consistently portraying Hamas as an "existential threat" and framing Israeli military actions as acts of legitimate national defence. Like The Guardian, The Telegraph initially emphasised the shock and urgency of the October 7 attacks. However, unlike The Guardian, it did not question the legitimacy of Israel's subsequent military action. Instead, its focus shifted toward strategic, military, and geopolitical concerns, a discursive practice that reinforced securitisation and excluded alternative interpretations. Although humanitarian suffering in Gaza was occasionally acknowledged, it was frequently framed as an inevitable consequence of Hamas's tactics. Coverage of Israeli airstrikes routinely included statements from Israeli officials characterising civilian casualties as tragic but unavoidable, rhetoric that further entrenched the security-first rationale. While dissenting or humanitarian perspectives were occasionally included, they remained subordinate to the dominant frame and were not allowed to challenge or reconfigure the overarching narrative.

The Sun employed the most divisive and populist angle, using its tabloid platform to reduce the conflict to a simple moral binary: Israelis were victims and Hamas were "monsters." Their coverage relied heavily on derogatory, dehumanising terms like "savages" and "bloodthirsty terrorists," and, at the level of discursive practice, systematically excluded Palestinian civilians from having a voice or offering a counter-narrative (Fairclough, 1995). The Sun's reporting on UK domestic events, particularly the vilification of pro-Palestinian protesters, extended the securitisation frame into the British context, reinforcing in-group/out-group boundaries (Van Dijk, 1998). This represents a clear example of the interaction between discursive and social practices in constructing and policing national identity. During the temporary ceasefire and hostage exchanges in November, The Sun highlighted the emotional reunions of Israeli families while portraying aid to Gaza as a transactional necessity rather than a humanitarian imperative. This framing cast humanitarian assistance as conditional, reinforcing the primacy of the security narrative and constraining the space for genuine empathy or cross-group solidarity.

Fairclough's model underscores the importance of temporal dynamics, revealing how the editorial logic of each outlet evolved in response to unfolding events. Following the October 7 attacks, all three newspapers initially adopted a highly securitised, event-driven narrative that foregrounded Israeli trauma and legitimised the military response. However, divergence soon emerged. The Guardian gradually incorporated humanitarian and legal discourses, particularly

as international concern mounted and mass protests in London drew hundreds of thousands calling for a ceasefire. Its coverage both reflected and shaped wider societal debates, illustrating the media's dual role as observer and participant in contesting the legitimacy of war (Fairclough, 1995). While The Telegraph acknowledged such developments, it largely retained a narrative centred on strategic patience and the imperative of defeating Hamas. Engagement with the ethics of military conduct remained limited and sporadic, even as the conflict became protracted. In contrast, The Sun sustained the intensity of its initial securitised narrative, remaining largely unresponsive to the rising civilian death toll in Gaza and to growing domestic and international calls for de-escalation. Its coverage further reinforced polarisation within the UK, portraying anti-war protesters as disloyal or traitorous, an example of how social practice functions to entrench exclusionary national identities (Fairclough, 1995).

The process of internationalisation, shaped by global legal frameworks and international diplomacy, further amplified the importance of these factors. The Guardian covered the conflict with a focus on global humanitarian norms and legal controversies, providing comprehensive coverage of United Nations' resolutions, the International Criminal Court, and critiques by global civil society – thus connecting textual reporting with wider social practices (Fairclough, 1995). The Telegraph approached internationalisation as a form of Western statecraft, emphasising US-UK diplomatic efforts, the risk of regional escalation, and the preservation of geopolitical alliances. In contrast, The Sun invoked international dimensions primarily to reinforce its core binaries, often linking the conflict to threats from Iran and amplifying fears of domestic extremism. These approaches further illustrate how discursive and social practices interact to shape distinct narrative logics, particularly in the construction of populist and securitised framings.

Debates concerning ceasefire and peace advocacy revealed the most pronounced editorial divisions. The Guardian not only covered anti-war demonstrations but also advocated for a humanitarian ceasefire, citing the striking levels of civilian suffering and the potential for further radicalisation. The Telegraph, along with official lines from US and UK capitals, branded calls for a quick ceasefire as strategically myopic and beneficial to Hamas. Meanwhile, The Sun dismissed advocacy for peace as a sign of lacking patriotism or as an act of treachery. Within these outlets, the presence or absence of dissenting voices illustrate the limits of identifiable public discourse set by editorial ideology.

Ultimately, the domestic political consequences of the conflict were filtered through each outlet's narrative concerns. The Guardian viewed dissent and resignations from Labour as sympathetic toward pro-Palestinian voices. In contrast, The Telegraph and The Sun cited such divisions as manifestations of leftist radicalism or failure of appropriate leadership. Throughout the press, unconditional condemnation of terror and antisemitism was uniform. However, supplemental coverage of protests and "community tensions" worked to challenge or reinforce dominant frames.

6.8. Conclusion

The analysis shows that British newspaper reporting on the Israel-Gaza war was shaped by both underlying editorial ideologies and the imperatives of media logic. An initial phase of consensus, framing the conflict primarily through a security lens, was followed by divergent emphases on humanitarian concern, ethical evaluation, and party-political alignments, producing distinct discursive environments for each outlet's audience. These dynamics are best understood through Fairclough's three-dimensional analytical model, which examines: the textual level (observable linguistic choices and visual elements), discursive practice (the

production and circulation of narratives, the inclusion or exclusion of voices, and genre conventions), and social practice (the wider socio-political context, including protest movements, policy debates, and the negotiation of national identity). Together, these processes shaped public understandings of violence and victimhood and defined the boundaries within which empathy, dissent, and political discourse could be articulated in British media coverage of the conflict.

7. Conclusion

The study of UK newspaper reporting during the 2023-24 Israel-Gaza conflict underscores the decisive influence of editorial ideology and institutional priorities. All three outlets initially adopted a security-centred narrative in the immediate aftermath of the 7 October 2023 attacks, framing Israeli actions as counter-terrorist imperatives. However, divergence soon followed. The Guardian progressively foregrounded humanitarian and legal dimensions, focusing on civilian casualties and invoking international legal norms. The Telegraph largely sustained alignment with government policy, reinforcing narratives of self-defence and strategic necessity while keeping humanitarian considerations peripheral. The Sun presented the conflict in emotive and partisan terms, consistently demonising Hamas and minimising Palestinian perspectives through a binary moral framework.

These contrasting narratives determined the selection of subjects and voices given prominence, thereby shaping audience perceptions, assessments of legitimacy, and collective debates about responsibility and justice. Framing proved central to influencing both public empathy and the nature of national discourse, with tangible implications for social cohesion and policy debate in the UK.

This dissertation makes both empirical and conceptual contributions. Empirically, it offers a detailed account of British media practices during a major geopolitical crisis, extending the work of Philo and Berry (2011) and Sirhan (2021). The analysis identifies not only persistent asymmetries in empathy and agency but also moments of editorial reflexivity, most evident in The Guardian, suggesting that coverage can potentially adapt in response to external critique. Conceptually, the integration of necropolitical analysis demonstrates how journalistic language and framing reinforce hierarchies of valued lives, expanding the understanding of media bias beyond political alignment to encompass the visibility and recognition of suffering.

The study has limitations. Its focus on British print media restricts the applicability of findings to other formats, such as digital platforms or international outlets. The qualitative nature of CDA, while methodologically rigorous, inevitably introduces interpretative subjectivity. In addition, the six-month temporal scope, covering the conflict's peak, may not capture longer-term discursive trajectories.

Future research could extend the scope to include broadcast, digital, and social media, as well as comparative analyses across national contexts. Audience reception studies would add further depth, clarifying how media constructions shape public understanding and mobilisation in relation to conflict. Finally, longitudinal designs could trace the evolution of framing and discourse over time, offering a richer account of the media's changing role in shaping collective interpretations of international crises.

Appendices

Appendix 1

Summary Table

No	Headline	Date	Word Count	Summary	Key Frames/ Themes	Rationale for Selection
THE GUARDIAN						
1	Israel and Hamas at war after surprise attacks from Gaza Strip	7 Oct 2023	~1,300	Hamas launched an unprecedented, combined rocket and ground assault from Gaza, resulting in numerous Israeli and Palestinian casualties. Israel declared a state of war, with both sides suffering significant losses and fears of broader escalation. The article details initial attacks, political and civilian reactions, and the regional context of recent unrest.	Securitisatio n, war/conflict, humanitarian crisis, resistance, terrorism, legitimacy, ethics of war	Illustrates the outbreak of the conflict, first reporting on escalation, covers both sides, introduces major frames used in subsequent coverage.
2	Hamas has taken a risk with its largest ever military blow to Israel	8 Oct 2023	~1,300	The article analyses Hamas's unprecedented attack on Israel, likening it to the 1973 Yom Kippur War in its surprise and scale. The author explores potential aims—forcing negotiations or assuming leadership in the West Bank—while highlighting devastating civilian casualties and the risk-laden political context. Israeli and Palestinian responses, regional dynamics, and the potential for further escalation are considered.	Securitisatio n, historical analogy, resistance, leadership struggle, humanitarian crisis, legitimacy, negotiation, risk	Representative expert opinion, illustrates nuanced framing, connects historical and current events, demonstrates complexity of framing and responsibility.
3	How the Hamas attack on the Supernova festival in Israel unfolded	9 Oct 2023	~1,300	The article provides a detailed reconstruction of the attack on the Supernova music festival, where Palestinian militants stormed a gathering of young Israelis, resulting in a mass shooting, chaos, abductions, and a significant civilian death toll. Eyewitness accounts and family testimonies highlight the horror, confusion, and aftermath of the event. The piece contextualises the attack within the broader outbreak of war.	Terrorism, humanitarian crisis, victimhood, chaos, trauma, resistance, abduction	Illustrative of civilian targeting, unique for focus on festival massacre, features strong emotive testimonies and first-person narratives.
4	In the midst of war, Benjamin Netanyahu is a liability who can only make things worse. He must go	9 Oct 2023	~1,500	This opinion piece argues that Prime Minister Benjamin Netanyahu's leadership has directly contributed to the eruption of war and ongoing violence. The author accuses Netanyahu of political failure, calls for his resignation, and criticises Israel's response as vengeful and unsustainable. The article also denounces Hamas's violence, discusses the international community's neglect, and urges urgent ceasefire and renewed peace talks.	Securitisatio n, leadership failure, legitimacy, responsibilit y, humanitarian crisis, international law, calls for negotiation/c easefire, ethics of war	Representative elite opinion, directly addresses leadership legitimacy and responsibility, foregrounds both internal and international frames.
5	Netanyahu says Israel's siege 'just getting started' – as it happened	10 Oct 2023	~2,000	This live blog documents events on the third day of the Israel-Hamas war, focusing on Israel's intensified airstrikes, the imposition of a full siege on Gaza, and Netanyahu's vow to "change the Middle East". It covers humanitarian impacts, international reactions, statements from Israeli and Hamas officials, and evolving casualty figures.	Securitisatio n, humanitarian crisis, escalation, siege, victimhood, resistance, legitimacy, international response, necropolitics	Captures escalation phase, documents evolving narratives, features direct discourse from all sides, provides granular, real-time framing of siege and humanitarian crisis.
6	More than 900 dead in Gaza since Saturday as shelling hits school, hospitals and homes	10 Oct 2023	~1,400	The article reports on mounting civilian casualties in Gaza as Israeli airstrikes hit residential areas, hospitals, and schools, and the only Egyptian border crossing. Humanitarian workers describe the unprecedented intensity of bombardment,	Humanitaria n crisis, collective punishment, securitisation , civilian	Highlights direct impact on civilians, documents destruction of infrastructure and health crisis,

				rising displacement, health system collapse, and lack of basic necessities. The UN and aid groups raise alarm over collective punishment and the urgent need for civilian protection.	victimhood, siege/blockade, international law, health system collapse	features humanitarian and UN voices, connects to international law frame.
7	Hamas gunmen 'killed families in their beds' at Kfar Aza kibbutz, say Israeli forces	11 Oct 2023	~1,200	The article documents the aftermath of the Hamas assault on Kfar Aza kibbutz, describing a "massacre" where Israeli forces report that entire families, including children, were killed and mutilated in their homes. Firsthand military and journalistic accounts detail scenes of devastation, horror, and rapid attack, with references to similar incidents in neighbouring communities. The piece highlights the vulnerability of civilians, the unpreparedness of security, and the scale of violence.	Massacre, civilian victimhood, securitisation, barbarity, trauma, war crimes, vulnerability, escalation	Graphic representation of violence against civilians, detailed firsthand testimonies, and focus on one of the most shocking and symbolic early incidents of the conflict
8	Killing civilians is indefensible, whether done by Hamas or Israel	12 Oct 2023	~1,200	This opinion article strongly condemns the killing of civilians by both Hamas and Israel, arguing that such acts are unjustifiable and violate the fundamental principles of international law and just war theory. The author details atrocities by both sides, criticises collective punishment of Gaza's population, and calls for upholding humanitarian norms. The piece critiques polarised public discourse and demands ethical restraint from all combatants.	Ethics of war, humanitarian crisis, collective punishment, legitimacy, international law, just war theory, polarisation	Provides a rare unequivocal condemnation of both sides, foregrounds international law and ethics, and problematises polarised media and public narratives.
9	Israel's darkest day: the 24 hours of terror that shook the country	13 Oct 2023	~2,200	This long-form feature reconstructs the sequence and scale of Hamas's surprise attack on southern Israel, covering the breach of the border, overrunning of military bases, massacre at the Supernova festival, and killings and abductions in kibbutzim. Drawing on video evidence, survivor testimonies, and military sources, it details Israeli intelligence failures, civilian vulnerability, and the resulting devastation.	Securitisation, intelligence failure, barbarity, civilian victimhood, trauma, war on terror, escalation, retaliation	Unparalleled narrative reconstruction of the attack's timeline and impact; synthesises eyewitness accounts, video analysis, and military perspectives; central to understanding Israeli framing of 7 October.
10	Seven days of terror that shook the world and changed the Middle East	14 Oct 2023	~2,800	This long-form report reconstructs the first week of the 2023 Israel-Gaza war, beginning with the Hamas attack on southern Israel, including the Supernova festival massacre, and following the subsequent Israeli bombardment of Gaza, mass displacement, hostage crisis, and regional political fallout. Drawing on multiple locations and perspectives, the article presents both Israeli trauma and Palestinian suffering, while situating the conflict in wider Middle Eastern geopolitics.	Securitisation, war on terror, humanitarian crisis, escalation, hostages, intelligence failure, regional spillover, legitimacy, resistance, trauma	Provides a comprehensive, multi-perspective reconstruction of the week's events, connecting local violence with regional and global consequences; combines forensic narrative, survivor testimony, political analysis, and humanitarian focus.
11	Israel-Gaza war: UN general assembly calls for 'immediate, durable humanitarian truce'	27 Oct 2023	~1,000	The article reports on the UN General Assembly's overwhelming vote for an "immediate, durable and sustainable humanitarian truce" in the Israel-Gaza war, demanding aid access to Gaza, protection of civilians, and the release of hostages. While not legally binding, the resolution signals global isolation of Israel and the US, calls for adherence to international law, and condemns attacks on all civilians. It exposes divisions over the conflict's framing and legitimacy.	Securitisation, international law, humanitarian crisis, legitimacy, ceasefire, hostage crisis, forced transfer, collective punishment, global isolation	Captures the global diplomatic response and legitimises humanitarian and legal frames; key for understanding international discursive contestation over the war.

12	The Observer view on antisemitism and Islamophobia: there is never any excuse	29 Oct 2023	~1,300	This editorial responds to a spike in antisemitism and Islamophobia in the UK following the 7 October Hamas attacks and Israel's military response. It condemns hate crimes against both Jews and Muslims, noting alarming increases in incidents, and urges that protest and criticism must not cross into hate or incitement. The article situates this within Britain's multi-ethnic democracy, discusses recent protest incidents, and asserts that there is no justification for hate, regardless of political context.	Hate crime, polarisation, securitisation, legitimacy, minority rights, protest, Islamophobia, antisemitism, identity, social cohesion	Offers a meta-perspective on the war's impact in the UK, analysing the intersection of international conflict, diasporic identity, and rising hate crimes; central to understanding how British media frames and contests hate in a tense political moment.
13	Anguish of Gaza residents as phones return to life with news of those lost	29 Oct 2023	~1,400	The article documents the aftermath of a 36-hour Israeli-imposed communications blackout in Gaza, focusing on the emotional devastation experienced by residents as news of deaths and destruction was revealed. Through direct testimonies, the piece details ongoing bombardment, humanitarian crisis, civilian displacement, the breakdown of basic services, and the impossibility of safety for Gaza's population.	Humanitarian crisis, communications blackout, civilian victimhood, trauma, siege, displacement, war crimes, necropolitics	Provides a rare, granular, and emotive account of everyday suffering and loss under siege, foregrounding voices of ordinary Gazans and humanitarian workers in real-time crisis.
14	Entire population of Gaza becoming 'dehumanised' says UN commissioner	30 Oct 2023	~1,100	The article reports UNRWA chief Philippe Lazzarini's address to the UN Security Council, warning that all Gazans are being "dehumanised" and subject to collective punishment by Israel. It highlights civilian suffering, a breakdown in civil order, dire humanitarian conditions, and warnings that a ceasefire is a matter of life and death. The piece details UN appeals, political divides over ceasefire, and the global struggle to end the violence.	Dehumanisation, humanitarian crisis, collective punishment, international law, securitisation, legitimacy, aid, ceasefire	Offers a unique institutional perspective, foregrounding the concept of dehumanisation and humanitarian law, and reveals the international debate over the Gaza crisis and the framing of civilian suffering.
15	Dozens killed after Israeli airstrikes on Gaza refugee camp	31 Oct 2023	~1,500	The article reports on Israeli airstrikes that destroyed apartment blocks in the Jabalia refugee camp, killing at least 50 and injuring about 150. Israel claims it targeted a Hamas commander, while Palestinian authorities call it a "heinous massacre". The piece documents escalating civilian casualties, dire humanitarian conditions, hostilities between Hamas and Israeli forces, and mounting international alarm over Gaza's situation.	Securitisation, humanitarian crisis, collective punishment, legitimacy, war crimes, civilian victimhood, international law, siege	Captures a major, highly controversial escalation in the war, combining on-the-ground reportage, statements from all parties, and wider humanitarian and legal context.
16	'We are all grieving': Israel falls silent to mark a month since Hamas attack	7 Nov 2023	~1,200	The article documents Israeli society's collective mourning a month after the 7 October Hamas attack. It details moments of national silence, vigils, and ceremonies to honour the 1,400 victims and 240 hostages, capturing grief, community, and ongoing trauma. It also addresses internal political divisions, debates about the government's response, and the wider context of continued military operations in Gaza, as well as the support for soldiers and bereaved families.	Grief, trauma, victimhood, national unity/division, hostage crisis, legitimacy, securitisation, militarisation	Illustrates the emotional landscape and internal contestations in Israeli society, foregrounding the social impacts of trauma, national mourning, and debates over the government's role and the ongoing war.
17	UK government challenged over ICC inquiry into Israel's conduct	12 Nov 2023	~1,300	The article details the political and legal debate in the UK regarding the International Criminal Court's (ICC) investigation into alleged war crimes by Israel in Gaza. It contrasts the Conservative government's rejection of ICC jurisdiction with Labour's support for legal inquiry and highlights the wider international contestation over international law, sovereignty, and humanitarian obligations in the context of the Israel-Gaza war.	Securitisation, international law, legitimacy, humanitarian crisis, sovereignty, war crimes, political contestation	Central for examining the UK's positioning within international legal debates, the politicisation of war crimes investigations, and the role of sovereignty and legitimacy in

						framing state conduct.
18	Families of hostages in Gaza wait to see if relatives among those freed	22 Nov 2023	~1,200	The article captures the agonising uncertainty and emotional turmoil experienced by the families of Israeli hostages held in Gaza as they await news of their loved ones' potential release amid a hostage exchange deal. It highlights diverse voices, individual stories, and the lack of clarity about who will be released, set against the backdrop of a negotiated ceasefire and ongoing war.	Hostage crisis, victimhood, humanitarian crisis, trauma, uncertainty, negotiation, family suffering, legitimacy	Provides a deeply personal lens on the hostage crisis, foregrounding family voices, the psychological toll of waiting, and the complexity of negotiated releases; humanises a central issue in the war's media framing.
19	US risks 'complicity in war crimes', says Human Rights Watch – as it happened	9 Dec 2023	~2200	This live blog covers developments as the US vetoes a UN Security Council resolution for a Gaza ceasefire. Human Rights Watch accuses the US of "complicity in war crimes" for supplying weapons and "diplomatic cover" to Israel. The article features UN and NGO reactions, humanitarian updates, and contrasting official statements from Israel, Hamas, the UK, and others.	Securitisation, war crimes, humanitarian crisis, legitimacy, ethics of war, international law, resistance, media framing	Exemplifies international and NGO discourse on legality and ethics; features vivid framing of US and Israeli actions; covers a pivotal moment in global diplomatic response.
20	South Africa launches case at UN court accusing Israel of genocide	29 Dec 2023	~1,200	The article reports South Africa's submission to the International Court of Justice (ICJ), accusing Israel of genocide in its Gaza campaign and demanding provisional measures for a ceasefire. It presents legal, political, and rhetorical reactions, including Israel's vehement rejection and the wider symbolic impact of such cases in international diplomacy.	Genocide, international law, securitisation, legitimacy, framing, humanitarian crisis, global narrative	Exemplifies how legal proceedings become arenas for international contest over narrative, legitimacy, and responsibility; highly relevant for analysing framing, necropolitics, and securitisation in media coverage.
21	ICJ case against Israel could finally empower the genocide convention	11 Jan 2024	~1,350	The article explores how South Africa's case against Israel at the ICJ could mark a turning point for the Genocide Convention. It reviews the legal, diplomatic, and symbolic significance of the proceedings, the rare use of state-to-state genocide litigation, and the historical and political factors shaping international justice.	Genocide, international law, legitimacy, securitisation, humanitarian crisis, impunity, legal precedent	Analyses the transformation of the Genocide Convention's role and meaning, using the Israel-Gaza case as a lens for shifts in global legal and political discourse.
22	'More killing won't bring back lost lives': Tal Mitnick, 18, on going to prison instead of joining IDF	23 Jan 2024	~1,700	The article profiles Tal Mitnick, an 18-year-old Israeli pacifist and conscientious objector, sentenced to prison for refusing to join the IDF after 7 October. Mitnick describes his motivations, public and familial reactions, the climate of militarisation in Israel, and the personal and social costs of dissent.	Conscientious objection, militarisation, resistance, human rights, securitisation, ethics of war, societal pressure	Unique and vivid account of Israeli anti-war dissent; humanises resistance, challenges mainstream militarist narrative, highlights youth perspectives.
23	ICJ to deliver interim ruling on genocide case against Israel on Friday	24 Jan 2024	~900	The article reports on the anticipation of the International Court of Justice's interim ruling in South Africa's genocide case against Israel. It outlines South Africa's confidence, Israel's strong rejection of the claims as "blood libel," and the possible consequences of a provisional ceasefire order. The piece highlights the legal, political, and humanitarian stakes, and references previous ICJ interventions.	Genocide, international law, securitisation, legitimacy, framing, humanitarian crisis, ceasefire	Captures a pivotal moment in international law and diplomacy; illustrates competing narratives and frames at a crucial juncture of the Israel-Gaza conflict.
24	Gaza death toll set to pass 30,000, as Israel prepares assault on Rafah	25 Feb 2024	~1,400	The article reports the imminent surpassing of 30,000 Palestinian deaths in Gaza as Israel plans an assault on Rafah, where 1.5 million displaced people are sheltering. It covers ongoing ceasefire negotiations, the	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, legitimacy, war ethics, framing,	Captures a critical moment of the Gaza war, with high civilian toll, impending military escalation, and

				humanitarian crisis, international pressure, and the intense local and political fallout.	resistance, hostages, impunity, international law	international diplomatic stakes.
25	Starvation in Gaza likely key to UK legal advice on war crimes	30 Mar 2024	~1,500	The article analyses growing international legal scrutiny over Israel's campaign in Gaza, focusing on accusations of war crimes, particularly the use of starvation as a weapon. It details the escalation of civilian suffering, accusations of collective punishment, and destruction of infrastructure, alongside Israel's justifications and international legal responses.	Humanitarian crisis, war crimes, international law, collective punishment, securitisation, legitimacy, domicile	Central case study of legal/ethical debates on collective punishment, humanitarian law, and shifting global perceptions of the conflict.
THE SUN						
1	Fury as Celtic fans unfurl pro-Palestinian banners after Hamas slaughter Israeli civilians with 200 dead in bloodbath	7 Oct 2023	~800	The article reports on Celtic football fans displaying pro-Palestinian banners just hours after Hamas attacks in Israel resulted in the deaths of hundreds of civilians. The event is framed as highly controversial, with criticism from former players and fans, while some supporters express gratitude.	Securitisation, war on terror, resistance, terrorism, legitimacy, ethics of protest	Illustrates UK tabloid framing, immediate reaction to 7 October, focus on legitimacy of protest and securitisation of Palestinian solidarity.
2	Netanyahu vows to reduce Gaza to 'rubble' as he blitzes Hamas in revenge for terror bloodbath dubbed 'Israel's 9/11'	8 Oct 2023	~2,300	The article reports on Israel's military response to Hamas' attack, described as "Israel's 9/11", with strong language around "vengeance" and "rubble". Israeli and UK leaders are quoted reaffirming Israel's right to defend itself, while visuals and emotive descriptions emphasise devastation and suffering. The narrative is heavily securitised, focusing on terror, revenge, and military power, with only brief mentions of Palestinian casualties and little contextualisation of broader causes.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Revenge, Humanitarian Crisis, Legitimacy, Terrorism, Ethics of War	Highly illustrative of sensationalist securitisation and militaristic framing; strong discursive patterns; emotive language and imagery; typical of tabloid style.
3	Chilling last message from missing Brit Jake Marlowe after Hamas gunmen 'kill 260' and send hundreds fleeing at festival	8 Oct 2023	~1,600	The article reports on the fate of British national Jake Marlowe, missing after the Hamas attack on a music festival near Gaza. It describes the attack's chaos and brutality, quoting family members and witnesses, and highlighting the scale of violence ("260 killed"). The coverage focuses on individual trauma, Western and Israeli perspectives, and highly emotive details, while references to Palestinian casualties are brief and largely statistical.	Securitisation, Terrorism, Humanitarian Crisis, Victimhood, Legitimacy, Media Spectacle	Highly emotive, human-interest framing; individual victim focus; example of tabloid securitisation and spectacle in conflict reporting.
4	Hostile aircraft did not soar into Israel from Lebanon as fears of 'second front' opening in war ruled out	11 Oct 2023	~1,300	The article reports that an apparent aerial threat from Lebanon was a false alarm, and clarifies that Israel is not facing a two-front war. It highlights the tense situation, with IDF statements, regional attacks by Hezbollah and PIJ, and mass mobilisation of Israeli forces. The narrative emphasises the threat of escalation, recent atrocities, and Israel's readiness for war, while minimising Palestinian perspectives.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Military Readiness, Escalation, Humanitarian Crisis, Legitimacy	Illustrates the British tabloid framing of escalation, fear of regional war, and securitisation logic; a typical example of event-driven, militarised crisis reporting
5	How evil Hamas commanders 'are training boy soldiers to battle Israeli forces preparing to storm Gaza'	15 Oct 2023	~1,200	The article alleges Hamas commanders are indoctrinating and militarising Palestinian boys, as young as 14, to fight against Israel. Using body-cam footage and social media, the narrative frames Hamas as "evil" and criminal, details atrocities committed, and describes child soldiers as victims of brainwashing. The piece centres on Israeli trauma and security responses, with highly emotive rhetoric and graphic detail.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Child Soldiers, Humanitarian Crisis, Indoctrination, Legitimacy, Dehumanisation	A vivid example of tabloid framing, weaponisation of children in narrative, and emotive securitisation discourse. Illustrates the ethics of war, civilian victimhood, and the portrayal of "evil" adversaries.
6	Inside Hamas' 311-mile tunnel labyrinth dubbed the 'Gaza Metro' where terrorists are	16 Oct 2023	~1,200	The article investigates the extensive tunnel system under Gaza, called the 'Gaza Metro', used by Hamas militants to hide, store weapons, and allegedly hold Israeli hostages. It describes the tunnels as a	Securitisation, Terrorism, War on Terror, Hostage	Strong example of securitisation and demonisation frames, blending war reporting with

	cowering 'with Israeli hostages'			defensive network built since 2007, full of booby traps, and central to Hamas' strategy against Israel. The piece features expert commentary, IDF statements, and details on the tunnels' role in the conflict.	Crisis, Militarisation, Humanitarian Threat	language emphasising threat and dehumanisation; illustrates how UK tabloids frame Hamas and the Gaza conflict.
7	Israel could lose hundreds of troops in bloodbath battle through booby-trapped maze of tunnels when they storm Gaza	16 Oct 2023	~1300	The article details the risks faced by Israeli troops as they prepare to storm Gaza's tunnel network, described as the "Gaza Metro". It warns of significant casualties due to booby traps and strategic planning by Hamas. The piece highlights intelligence sources, quotes military experts, and describes the tactical advantages Hamas is believed to hold underground. Civilian suffering and humanitarian issues are briefly mentioned, as are casualties and hostages.	Securitisation, Terrorism, Humanitarian Crisis, War on Terror, Resistance, Legitimacy, Ethics of War	Selected as a clear example of tabloid securitisation framing, intense militarised rhetoric, and for its coverage of both military and humanitarian stakes.
8	Hamas commander Jihad Mheisen killed along with his family as Israel blows up his house in assassination blitz	19 Oct 2023	~950	The article reports on the Israeli airstrike that killed a key Hamas commander, Jihad Mheisen, along with his family in Gaza City. It details similar recent strikes on senior Hamas figures, contextualises these killings within the broader Israeli response to the October 7 Hamas attacks, and notes the heavy civilian toll. The piece references official statements and reactions, highlights escalating violence, and mentions international leaders' visits and commentary.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Assassination, Humanitarian Crisis, Legitimacy, Resistance, International Law	Selected for its direct framing of targeted killings/assassination, juxtaposition of military and civilian deaths, and illustrative tabloid securitisation discourse.
9	Iranian banks accused of funnelling millions of pounds to Hamas are operating in heart of London	21 Oct 2023	~900	The article reveals that two Iranian banks, Bank Saderat and Melli Bank, accused of channelling funds to Hamas, continue to operate in central London despite US sanctions and public criticism. The piece frames these institutions as direct supporters of terrorism and calls for urgent UK government action, linking Iran, its banks, and the Islamic Revolutionary Guard to Hamas attacks. Voices of UK politicians demand stricter sanctions and banning of the Iranian Guard, amplifying the narrative of security threat within Britain.	Securitisation, Terrorism Financing, Legitimacy, War on Terror, State Sponsorship, Political Pressure	Selected for its explicit securitisation frame, focus on terrorism financing, and as an example of how tabloid discourse constructs links between foreign states, terrorism, and domestic (UK) security policy.
10	I'd do anything to free my mum and brother, says distraught relative of Brits dragged away by Hamas monsters	21 Oct 2023	~1100	The article reports on the anguish of a British-Israeli woman whose mother and brother were taken hostage by Hamas during the invasion of Israel. It covers the impact on families, the ongoing hostage negotiations, mass protests in London, and official responses. The narrative juxtaposes the personal suffering with the wider political and security context, highlighting calls for both humanitarian release and robust security action.	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, terrorism, hostage-taking, legitimacy, protest	Illustrates the intersection of personal tragedy, political discourse, securitisation, and media framing of hostages and protests; vivid emotional narrative and social context.
11	Israel's war in Gaza is 'do or die' says PM Benjamin Netanyahu after vow to 'cut head off the snake' of Iran	22 October 2023	~1200	The article covers Israeli Prime Minister Netanyahu's statements calling the Gaza war "do or die" and warning Iran and Hezbollah against opening new fronts. It reports on Israel's intensifying military preparations, threats of large-scale retaliation, and regional/international reactions.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Legitimacy, Escalation, Humanitarian Crisis	Exemplifies securitising discourse, escalation rhetoric, and the interlinkage of Gaza conflict with Iran and Hezbollah.
12	Being PAID £8k to snatch hostages and selfies with child captives...Hamas brutes' unimaginable terror in their own words	24 Oct 2023	~1250	The article reports on interrogation footage of Hamas operatives who participated in the October 7 attacks. The operatives describe receiving financial rewards for kidnapping Israelis, using civilians as human shields, and carrying out killings, including of women and children. It highlights harrowing details of the violence, referencing the trauma of survivors and the tactics used by militants.	Securitisation, Terrorism, Dehumanisation, Humanitarian Crisis, War Ethics	Chosen for its explicit representation of the "terror threat" and "securitisation" frame, with direct focus on perpetrators' accounts and emotive survivor testimony.

Th e Su n 13	Ten charity workers among hundreds held by Hamas terrorists – with nine volunteers murdered by savages	25 Oct 2023	~1,400	The article describes the fate of charity workers from "Road to Recovery," who provided medical transport for Palestinian children but became hostages or victims in the Hamas attacks. It details personal stories, the charity's cross-border humanitarian work, and the aftermath of violence, including the murder of nine volunteers and the kidnapping of others. Released hostages' testimonies, Israeli and international reactions, and the broader war context are also presented.	Securitisation, Humanitarian Crisis, Victimhood, War Ethics, Terrorism, Resistance, Legitimacy	Strong example of personalisation and victim framing, the humanitarian crisis frame, and the ethics of war in UK popular media. Highlights interplay of securitisation and humanisation discourses.
Th e Su n 14	Hundreds join peaceful rally outside UK Qatari embassy to plead for return of over 200 Israeli hostages taken by Hamas	29 Oct 2023	~650	The article reports on a peaceful rally in London, where families and supporters gathered outside the UK Qatari embassy to urge action for the release of Israeli hostages held by Hamas. Protesters held photos of abducted loved ones, read out hostages' names, and called on Qatar to mediate. Emotional testimonies from family members highlighted the distress and urgency of the situation. Symbolic acts such as singing hymns and distributing yellow ribbons were used to raise awareness.	Hostage crisis, humanitarian appeal, securitisation, emotional testimony, diplomatic pressure	Illustrates public mobilisation, emotional and symbolic responses to hostage crisis, and calls for third-party intervention.
Th e Su n 15	Shani Louk 'tortured and beheaded' by Hamas in 'unfathomable horror' claims Israel after skull fragment of German found	30 Oct 2023	~1,600	The article reports on the death of Shani Louk, a German-Israeli woman kidnapped at the Supernova festival during the October 7 Hamas attack. Israel claims she was tortured and beheaded by Hamas, though some details are disputed. The piece highlights the suffering of her family, the use of graphic imagery, and official Israeli and family reactions. It also describes wider Israeli retaliation and the ongoing humanitarian toll.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Humanitarian Crisis, Barbarity, Legitimacy, Victimhood	Selected for its highly emotional framing, graphic portrayal, and as a vivid example of securitising discourse and dehumanisation in tabloid reporting.
Th e Su n 16	Israel storms Hamas stronghold in 10-hour gun battle & destroy 130 tunnels as terrorists 'losing control of north Gaza'	9 Nov 2023	~900	The article details Israeli troops capturing a significant Hamas outpost in Gaza following a ten-hour battle. The IDF claims dozens of militants were killed, and over 130 tunnels destroyed, asserting loss of Hamas control in the north. The narrative highlights Israeli military progress and the tunnel network's strategic importance, with references to civilian casualties and the contested use of hospitals as Hamas command centres.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Legitimacy, Humanitarian Crisis, Resistance, Terrorism	Chosen for its explicit securitisation framing, focus on military progress, and rhetorical strategies in representing both Israeli and Palestinian actors.
Th e Su n 17	First Israeli hostages set to be freed in HOURS as four-day ceasefire begins after nearly 50 days of fighting	24 Nov 2023	~1,100	The article reports on the beginning of a four-day ceasefire between Israel and Hamas after nearly 50 days of conflict, with the first group of Israeli hostages (women and children) to be released by Hamas in exchange for Palestinian prisoners. The ceasefire is portrayed as fragile and temporary, with warnings from Israeli officials that the war is not over. The piece includes images and statements from both sides, describes the humanitarian toll on Gaza's civilians, and notes the mediating role of Qatar, the US, and Egypt.	Ceasefire, Hostage Exchange, Humanitarian Crisis, War, Securitisation, Legitimacy, Mediation	Captures a pivotal moment (initiation of the first truce), highlights framing of hostages and humanitarian crisis, and exemplifies themes of securitisation and mediation.
18	Israeli peace activist murdered by Hamas on October 7 sends message from beyond the grave to country's children	27 Nov 2023	~1,250	The article tells the story of Lilach Kipnis, an Israeli peace activist and child trauma expert, murdered during the October 7 Hamas attack on Be'eri kibbutz. It describes her legacy through a book she wrote to help Israeli children cope with trauma from war and violence. The book is to be distributed nationally, backed by the Israeli president, and represents a message of hope. The article features emotional testimonies from her family, narratives of surviving children, and the continuing impact of trauma on Israeli society.	Humanitarian crisis, trauma, legacy, hope, war's impact on civilians, resistance to fear, memory, Israeli victimhood, peace activism, children in conflict	Unique humanisation of an Israeli victim, focus on civilian trauma, the role of memory and legacy in wartime, and illustration of non-combatant resistance.

19	Twisted Hamas fighters 'playing recordings of Israeli kids screaming "save me, save me" to lure troops into booby traps'	19 Dec 2023	~1,300	The article reports Israeli government claims that Hamas is using psychological warfare against Israeli troops, including playing recordings of children screaming and booby-trapping children's toys to lure soldiers into death traps. It includes IDF and official spokesperson statements, alleged descriptions of Hamas tactics, and discussion of recent civilian and hostage casualties, including the shooting of hostages and the killing of a mother and daughter in a church. The article reflects both Israeli and some international perspectives, highlighting the psychological and ethical dimensions of the conflict.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Psychological Warfare, Humanitarian Crisis, Ethics of War, Legitimacy, Victimhood	Strong representation of securitisation and psychological warfare frames; the article offers insight into Israeli narratives, justification strategies, and highlights key turning points (e.g., civilian deaths, hostage tragedies) that shaped public perception.
20	Israeli PM Benjamin Netanyahu vows war with Hamas 'isn't close to finished' during trip to northern Gaza	25 Dec 2023 (published 19:08; updated 26 Dec 2023, 1:02)	~950	Israeli PM Netanyahu visited IDF soldiers in northern Gaza, vowing to continue the war against Hamas until their defeat. The article describes Israel's intensified ground operations, Hamas's refusal of a ceasefire, and the humanitarian consequences, including massive displacement and casualties. Netanyahu emphasises soldier safety and national resolve.	Securitisation, war on terror, humanitarian crisis, legitimacy, resistance, ethics of war	Illustrates the Israeli leadership's public stance, a hard securitisation frame, and juxtaposes military aims with humanitarian consequences.
21	Israel on high alert for 'revenge attacks' as Iran blames them for bombing that killed 100 & Hezbollah vows 'punishment'	4 Jan 2024	~1100	The article reports that Israel is on high alert following threats of revenge from Iran and Hezbollah after bombings in Iran and Lebanon killed over 100 people, including a top Hamas chief and a Hezbollah leader. Iran blames Israel for the attacks and vows retribution, while Hezbollah threatens a "severe reaction." The piece details escalating rhetoric, fears of regional war, and international calls for restraint, notably from the UN and French President Macron.	Securitisation, Retaliation, Regional Escalation, War on Terror, Legitimacy, Resistance, Humanitarian Risks	Chosen as a vivid example of media framing an imminent regional conflict, with explicit discussion of threat perception, retaliation, and the potential for broader Middle East escalation.
22	Israeli student 'alive' 100 days after she was seen begging 'don't kill me' as Hamas snatched her from music festival	15 Jan 2024	~700	The article focuses on Noa Argamani, a 26-year-old Israeli woman abducted by Hamas from the Nova festival on 7 October 2023. Footage of her abduction went viral, making her a symbol of the attacks. 100 days later, new video clips released by Hamas suggest she and two other hostages are alive. The article details the massacre at the festival, reactions from the families, and the broader hostage crisis.	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, terrorism, victimhood, hostage diplomacy, media symbolism	Provides a vivid, emotive case study of hostage framing; demonstrates use of emotive imagery and victimhood narratives; reflects broader hostage and terror discourses.
23	Israel confirms it's FLOODING Hamas terror tunnels with sea water to flush out Gaza fighters & destroy underground HQs	30 Jan 2024	~1100	Israel's military confirms using sea water to flood Hamas tunnels under Gaza, aiming to neutralise fighters and destroy underground HQs. The article details tactics, justifications, and concerns about civilian risks and hostages. It provides broader context of tunnel warfare, IDF strategies, and the humanitarian impact in Gaza.	Securitisation, war on terror, counter-terrorism, military innovation, humanitarian crisis, ethics of war	Demonstrates a clear case of securitisation discourse, highlights military innovation and humanitarian debate, and links media framing of Israel-Hamas conflict.
24	'Gaza's Bin Laden' Yahya Sinwar is FILMED fleeing in terror tunnel as Israel vows to catch brute 'dead or alive'	14 Feb 2024	~1200	The article reports on the Israeli military's release of footage allegedly showing Hamas leader Yahya Sinwar fleeing through Gaza's tunnels with his family. Sinwar is heavily labelled as a "terror chief" and "Gaza's Bin Laden," accused of masterminding the October 7 attacks. Israel vows to capture him "dead or alive." The article frames Sinwar's escape as cowardly, contrasts his actions with Israeli rescue efforts, and highlights his criminal past.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Terrorism, Legitimacy, Dehumanisation	Represents strong securitisation and demonisation frame; unique in focusing on personalising the "hunt" for Sinwar.
25	Israel 'offers to release 800 Palestinian prisoners' including 100 murderers in	25 Mar 2024	~1250	Israel is reportedly considering releasing up to 800 Palestinian prisoners, including 100 convicted of murder, in exchange for 40 hostages held by Hamas since October 7. The proposal comes amidst increasing protests against Netanyahu's government	Hostage exchange, securitisation, humanitarian crisis,	This article was selected for its vivid representation of the evolving hostage negotiation dynamic,

	deal with Hamas to release 40 hostages			and international pressure for a hostage deal. While Israel insists on continuing its military objectives, Hamas demands any deal must include an end to the war. The article describes failed negotiations, ongoing humanitarian concerns in Gaza, and the complex political context, including a planned Israeli offensive on Rafah.	legitimacy, resistance, war ethics, peace negotiations	showcasing securitisation and humanitarian frames, and capturing a critical moment of political tension and public protest in Israel.
THE TELEGRAPH						
1	Hamas terrorists butcher civilians as stunned Israel suffers '9/11' moment	07 Oct 2023	~1400	The article reports on Hamas's large-scale surprise attack on Israel, describing mass civilian killings, hostage-taking, and widespread shock, framing the event as Israel's '9/11'. It covers the immediate military and political responses, reactions from world leaders, and fears of wider regional escalation. The piece provides graphic details and strongly condemns Hamas while contextualising Israeli actions as justified retaliation.	Securitisation, Terrorism, War on Terror, Humanitarian Crisis, Legitimacy, Retaliation, Regional Escalation	A paradigmatic example of securitising, strongly framed reporting in the immediate aftermath of the attack, with clear 'terror' frame and intense emotive language; ideal for CDA illustration.
2	Israel pounds Gaza with one of heaviest ever missile assaults ahead of ground invasion	9 Oct 2023	~1500	The article describes Israel's massive aerial bombardment of Gaza following a deadly Hamas attack, detailing destruction, civilian casualties, preparations for a ground invasion, and a humanitarian crisis as Israel cuts electricity and restricts exits. Hamas threatens to execute hostages, and both sides are engaged in escalating violence. Testimonies from both Israeli and Palestinian sides illustrate chaos, fear, and devastation.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Humanitarian Crisis, Legitimacy, Resistance, Terrorism	Illustrates escalation and multi-faceted framing: military, humanitarian, securitisation. Represents early, high-intensity stage of conflict and typical mainstream British coverage.
3	Supernova Music Festival: At least 260 dead in Israel after Hamas terrorist attack	09 Oct 2023	~1,100	The article details the Hamas attack on the Supernova music festival near Kibbutz Re'im in Israel's Negev Desert, where at least 260 people were killed. It describes the chaos as partygoers tried to escape, the trauma of survivors and families searching for loved ones, and the rising overall death toll. The article uses first-person accounts and focuses on the brutality of the attack, hostages taken, and the international impact as many attendees were foreign nationals.	Securitisation, Terrorism, Humanitarian Crisis, Dehumanisation, Legitimacy, Victimhood	Illustrates securitisation and dehumanisation frames; one of the most widely reported and symbolic civilian mass casualty events at the conflict's onset; provides emotional depth through survivor and family testimonies.
4	Israeli intelligence wrongly concluded Hamas would not launch a full invasion	08 Oct 2023	~1,100	The article details how Israeli intelligence misjudged Hamas's intentions, believing the group wanted to avoid direct conflict with Israel. This miscalculation led to a massive, meticulously planned assault by Hamas, resulting in high civilian and military casualties. Israeli media and officials describe the event as the country's gravest security failure in 50 years. The article explores both the intelligence errors and public/political fallout, with some voices calling for accountability.	Intelligence failure, securitisation, terrorism, legitimacy, war ethics, crisis	Illustrates a pivotal intelligence and securitisation frame, marking a major turning point in the conflict narrative and discourse on security failures.
5	Kfar Aza kibbutz: Babies killed in Hamas attack as Israeli death toll passes 1,000	10 Oct 2023	~1,300	The article reports on the aftermath of the Hamas attack on Kfar Aza kibbutz, where Israeli soldiers found the bodies of civilians, including babies and children. Israeli officials compare the massacre to Nazi pogroms, and the article describes scenes of brutality, referencing unverifiable claims of beheadings. The IDF's response and US political support are also covered, as are casualties in Gaza and regional escalation.	Securitisation, war on terror, humanitarian crisis, barbarity, legitimacy, terrorism	This article offers a vivid and emotionally charged account of the massacre, is heavily cited in discourse on the conflict, and is a salient example of securitisation and atrocity framing.
6	IDF ground invasion: Israel orders 1.1m Palestinians to evacuate from northern Gaza	13 Oct 2023	~850	The article reports that Israel ordered 1.1 million Palestinians to evacuate northern Gaza within 24 hours, ahead of a planned ground invasion to target Hamas. The military frames this as necessary for civilian safety, while the UN and Hamas dispute the evacuation order's legitimacy and feasibility. The piece highlights the scale of	Securitisation, Humanitarian Crisis, War on Terror, Legitimacy, Displacement	Illustrates mass civilian displacement order, acute framing of humanitarian crisis, and clear interplay between securitisation and

				civilian displacement, ongoing bombardment, and competing narratives around responsibility and humanitarian impact.		legitimacy discourses.
7	How Israel targets the 'Gaza Metro' of Hamas tunnels hiding terrorists	13 Oct 2023	~1100	The article investigates Israel's strategies to target and destroy Hamas' extensive underground tunnel network—dubbed the 'Gaza Metro'—used for military command, concealment, and movement of weapons. It describes the tunnels' complexity, their strategic value, and the challenges posed to Israeli forces, including the risk of casualties, booby traps, and the use of human shields. The narrative contextualises the tunnels within the broader Israel-Hamas conflict and highlights differing claims over their destruction.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Legitimacy, Resistance, Urban Warfare, Humanitarian Crisis	Offers a detailed example of securitisation framing, connects military strategy with discourse on legitimacy, resistance, and humanitarian risk.
8	Humanitarian crisis in Gaza 'a priority', says Joe Biden	14 Oct 2023	~2,500	The article reports on the ongoing Israel-Hamas conflict, highlighting the growing humanitarian crisis in Gaza as a result of Israeli airstrikes and impending ground operations. US President Joe Biden emphasises the importance of addressing the crisis and distinguishes between Hamas and the broader Palestinian population. The article covers responses from global leaders, evacuation orders, regional protests, and the mounting civilian toll.	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, right to defend, war on terror, international law, civilian suffering, political responses	Selected as it exemplifies the intersection of humanitarian discourse with securitisation, shows Western political framing, and covers a critical turning point in the escalation and global response.
9	Israel kills Hamas leader Bilal al Kedra who masterminded kibbutz Nirim and Nir Oz attacks	15 Oct 2023	~650	The article reports that the Israeli Defence Forces (IDF) killed Bilal al Kedra, a Hamas commander allegedly behind the Nirim and Nir Oz kibbutz attacks. The article details the IDF's ongoing strikes in Gaza, noting heavy air raids, the death of other operatives, and the preparation for a possible ground incursion. The Gaza Health Ministry is cited regarding Palestinian civilian casualties. The piece also highlights hostage rescue as an IDF priority and mentions U.S. military movements in the region.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Legitimacy, Humanitarian Crisis, Hostage/Rescue	Illustrates the securitisation frame, highlights the targeted killing rationale, covers escalation and broader regional context, and juxtaposes military and humanitarian narratives.
10	Humza Yousaf's wife says Israeli 'terror' has left family 'waiting to die'	15 Oct 2023	~900	The article reports on Nadia El-Nakla's emotional speech at the SNP conference, where she accuses Israel of "terrorising" Gaza. She shares the desperation of her trapped family, the collapse of healthcare, and the use of ice cream trucks for the dead. An emergency SNP motion called for UK support of a humanitarian corridor. The article contextualises her family's situation within the wider conflict, quoting both her and her husband, Scotland's First Minister.	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, terror, victimhood, legitimacy, emotional suffering	Highlights direct testimony of civilian suffering; illustrates humanitarian and securitisation frames through a high-profile political and personal narrative.
11	Six scenarios for the endgame of Israel's invasion of Gaza	16 Oct 2023	~2,100	This article outlines six possible endgame scenarios for Israel's military campaign in Gaza, including destroying Hamas, dividing or occupying Gaza, mass displacement, failed offensives, regional escalation, and even global war. It analyses military, political, and humanitarian implications of each path, referencing international and regional actors' responses.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Humanitarian Crisis, Geopolitical Risk, Legitimacy, Displacement, Escalation, Ethics of War	The article offers a comprehensive strategic overview, capturing key frames, uncertainties, and the spectrum of potential outcomes, making it valuable for mapping dominant narratives and strategic framings.
12	Family of British-Israeli girls caught in Hamas attack describe their heartbreak	17 Oct 2023	~1,500	The article narrates the personal tragedy of the Sharabi family after the Hamas attack on Kibbutz Be'eri, focusing on two teenage sisters—one confirmed killed, the other missing—and their British-Israeli background. The narrative weaves together interviews with relatives, vivid depictions of family life, and the uncertainty and anguish following the assault. The story is	Humanitarian crisis, victimhood, securitisation, personalisation of conflict,	Selected as a highly personalised, emotive example of civilian suffering, showing the humanitarian and psychological impact of the attack, and how British

				framed through human interest, linking individual grief to broader geopolitical consequences and the complexities of British-Israeli identity.	transnational identity	nationals are entangled in the conflict.
13	Israel and Hamas trade blame over Gaza hospital deaths	18 Oct 2023	~1,900	The article details the explosion at Gaza's Ahli Arab Hospital, exploring how both Israel and Hamas blamed each other for the incident. It chronicles the rapid proliferation of conflicting narratives, media reactions, and the use of propaganda. The article incorporates analyses from military experts, visual evidence, official statements, and the impact on regional protests. Ultimately, the piece highlights the difficulty of establishing truth amid information warfare and deep distrust.	Securitisation, Propaganda War, Humanitarian Crisis, Legitimacy, Disinformation, Media Framing, Ethics of War	Offers a vivid case study of media framing, blame attribution, and securitisation, highlighting how a single event can be interpreted through competing narratives and trigger international political consequences.
14	Rishi Sunak says Britain wants Israel 'to win' its war as he visits Benjamin Netanyahu in Tel Aviv	19 Oct 2023	~1100	UK Prime Minister Rishi Sunak visited Israel to express strong support for the country following the October 7 Hamas attack. Sunak stated that Britain wants Israel "to win" and stands with Israel in its "darkest hour". He recognised the suffering of both Israelis and Palestinians, highlighted the humanitarian crisis in Gaza, and backed efforts to allow aid into the territory. Sunak's visit was part of a wider diplomatic push to prevent regional escalation, involving parallel efforts by US and UK officials in the Middle East.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Humanitarian Crisis, Legitimacy, Solidarity, International Diplomacy	Illustrates explicit securitisation and solidarity frame, reveals UK government's public position, covers both humanitarian and security themes in the immediate aftermath of the Hamas attack.
15	Hamas greatest terror threat to the West since Islamic State, warns FBI director in US	31 Oct 2023	~950	The article reports on FBI Director Christopher Wray's testimony to the US Senate, warning that Hamas now poses the most significant terror threat to the West since ISIS. Wray argues that the Gaza conflict risks radicalising new jihadists and inspiring global terror attacks. The piece also covers warnings from US Secretary of State Antony Blinken about worsening humanitarian conditions in Gaza, potential domestic threats in the US and UK, and the political debate over ceasefires and humanitarian aid.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Terrorism, Humanitarian Crisis, Radicalisation, Legitimacy, Threat Perception	Strong illustration of securitisation frame, official narrative linkage of Hamas to global jihadist threat, highlights Western security discourse and policy responses.
16	Gaza's Egypt border was finally opened - but it could be short-lived	01 Nov 2023	~1650	The Rafah border crossing between Gaza and Egypt was opened for a limited group of foreign nationals and wounded Palestinians amid the ongoing conflict. The article details the chaotic evacuation process, complex negotiations between Israel, Egypt, Hamas, and international actors, and the fragile nature of the agreement. The piece highlights humanitarian concerns, the political dynamics at play, and the precarious situation for civilians left behind.	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, war ethics, border politics, international diplomacy	Illustrates the intersection of humanitarian access, securitisation, and political negotiation. Provides a vivid case study of border politics and the lived experience of civilians amidst securitisation discourse.
17	Hamas, not Israel, is perpetrating 'collective punishment' in Gaza	04 Nov 2023	~1100	The article argues that accusations against Israel of collective punishment in Gaza are legally and morally flawed, insisting Israel's actions are aimed at defeating Hamas and preventing future attacks, not punishing civilians. It claims that Hamas itself commits genuine collective punishment against Gazans by weaponising civilians, stealing aid, and blocking evacuations. The author criticises international organisations and human rights groups for misattributing blame and perpetuating Hamas' tactics.	Securitisation, Legitimacy, Humanitarian Crisis, Terrorism, Ethics of War	Presents an explicit counter-narrative to dominant accusations against Israel; illustrates securitisation framing and the ethics of war; valuable for examining legitimacy and blame attribution.
18	Ceasefire in Israel-Hamas war will never bring peace, says Biden	18 Nov 2023	~2,500	The article covers live updates on the Israel-Hamas war, with a focus on President Biden's rejection of a ceasefire as a path to peace, citing Hamas's "ideology of destruction." It details humanitarian concerns, ongoing hostilities, hostage issues, and diplomatic rifts over post-war governance of Gaza.	Securitisation, war on terror, humanitarian crisis, legitimacy, international law,	Selected for its prominent articulation of securitisation discourse, high-level framing by Western leaders, and multi-actor debate on

					resistance, civilian casualties	humanitarian vs. security logics.
19	Israel is winning. It won't give up the fight now	22 Nov 2023	~950	The article analyses Israel's stance after agreeing to a temporary hostage deal with Hamas, highlighting that Israeli leadership remains committed to eradicating Hamas despite international and internal pressures for a broader ceasefire. It explores the strategic, political, and diplomatic dimensions behind Israel's decision, referencing pressures from the US, Israeli public, and the complexity of hostage negotiations. The author argues that Israel's military and political objectives make a full cessation of hostilities unlikely until Hamas is dismantled, framing the conflict as pivotal for the future of Israeli security and regional diplomacy.	Securitisation, legitimacy, right to defend, humanitarian crisis, war on terror	This article typifies a securitisation and "war on terror" framing in British media, showing narrative legitimization of ongoing military action and representing a pivotal moment in diplomatic negotiations.
20	How Israel's invasion of Gaza risks radicalising a new generation of Palestinians	08 Dec 2023	~2100	The article documents the devastation caused by Israeli airstrikes in Gaza, focusing on the Jabaliya refugee camp and the broader destruction. It highlights civilian suffering, the psychological impact on children, and the risk of radicalisation among Palestinians. Israeli justifications for military action and international reactions are discussed. The narrative weaves personal stories with broader geopolitical implications, questioning the proportionality of Israel's response and warning of long-term consequences for the region.	Humanitarian crisis, radicalisation, securitisation, war ethics, legitimacy, collective punishment, trauma	Provides a detailed, emotive account of the humanitarian and psychological toll of the conflict; illustrates media framing of civilian impact and the cycle of radicalisation; useful for CDA of trauma and securitisation frames.
21	The International Court of Justice has been weaponised against the Jewish state	07 Jan 2024	~1200	The article argues that South Africa's ICJ case against Israel represents an abuse of international law, labelling it "lawfare" in support of Hamas. The author contends that the genocide accusation is both unfounded and politically motivated, and that it threatens to undermine the integrity of international legal institutions. Israel's actions are framed as self-defence against terrorism, while the ICJ process is depicted as a vehicle for anti-Israel propaganda.	Securitisation, Lawfare, Legitimacy, Propaganda, International Law, Terrorism	Represents a clear "lawfare"/securitisation frame; illustrates international legal contestation and framing of Israel/Palestine as existential threats.
22	Rising hunger in Gaza 'turning children into skeletons'	08 Jan 2024	~1900	The article details the dramatic escalation of malnutrition and hunger in Gaza, with experts warning that an entire generation is at risk of irreversible damage. It highlights the unique scale of food insecurity, exacerbated by conflict, blockade, and aid restrictions. The narrative focuses on children and infants facing starvation and disease, explores failed humanitarian efforts, and emphasises the dire consequences of sustained deprivation and infrastructural collapse.	Humanitarian crisis, famine risk, necropolitics, securitisation, ethics of war, international aid, vulnerability of children	Chosen for its in-depth focus on the humanitarian/necropolitical dimension, rare data on famine risk, and its vivid depiction of the consequences of the conflict beyond immediate violence.
23	Israel discovers tunnel 'wide enough for Hamas leader to drive his car down'	17 Jan 2024	~1200	The article reports that Israeli forces have discovered an extensive Hamas tunnel network under Gaza, with some tunnels large enough to accommodate vehicles. Israeli officials estimate the tunnels stretch up to 450 miles, much more than previously thought. The destruction of these tunnels is described as central to Israel's war aims. The piece also covers humanitarian concerns, aid deals brokered by Qatar and France, and international reactions, including UN calls for a ceasefire.	Securitisation, War on Terror, Legitimacy, Humanitarian Crisis	Exemplifies the securitisation and military framing of Hamas, and covers both military strategy and humanitarian issues in a single article.
24	Children 'starting to die from malnutrition' in northern Gaza as food crisis worsens	22 Feb 2024	~1200	The article details a worsening humanitarian crisis in northern Gaza, where children are reportedly dying from malnutrition due to widespread food shortages and the suspension of food aid. UN agencies and NGOs warn of a looming famine and describe the situation as	Humanitarian crisis, famine, securitisation, child mortality, ethics of war	Represents an acute case of humanitarian crisis framing, highlights civilian suffering and breakdown of aid, and provides clear

				unprecedented, with medical workers reporting a significant number of child deaths. Aid convoys have been looted and attacked, making deliveries nearly impossible. Calls for immediate action emphasise the need to resume humanitarian assistance.		data for CDA on necropolitics and securitisation logics.
25	This Ramadan in Gaza, there will be no dates to break the fast	15 Mar 2024	~1200	The article details the dire humanitarian situation in Gaza as Ramadan begins, with food shortages so severe that families must eat leaves and animal food. The Israeli blockade and the destruction of agriculture have left the population in famine, with children dying from malnutrition and dehydration. International humanitarian efforts are described as insufficient amid escalating violence. The article ends with a call for genuine peace and humanitarian access.	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, ethics of war, famine, international law, collective punishment	Provides a vivid, emotive account of the everyday impact of war and blockade, linking humanitarian crisis directly to ongoing conflict and international obligations.

Appendix 2

Coding and Analytical Grid

No	Actor Portrayal	Key Terms/ Labels	Agency/ Voice	Frame	Discourse	Emotive/ Rhetorical Language
THE GUARDIAN						
1	<p> Hamas: “Militant group”, “Islamists”, “fighters”, “gunmen”, “terrorist organisation” (per IDF). Aggressors launching attacks and retaliators against Israeli policy.</p> <p> Israel: State actor under attack, defenders, victims, military responders, declared state of war.</p> <p> Civilians: Palestinian victims of airstrikes, Israeli victims of attacks.</p> <p> International actors: IDF (institutional voice), political leaders (Netanyahu, Mohammed Deif).</p>	<p> Militants, fighters, terrorist organisation, reservists, civilian and military hostages, aggression, retaliatory airstrikes, uprising, intifada, blockade, freedom of movement, infiltration, crisis, devastating toll.</p>	<p> Hamas: Active (launched attack, infiltrated towns, issued statements).</p> <p> Israel: Active/reactive (declared war, airstrikes, mobilised reservists).</p> <p> Civilians: Passive (quoted for emotional impact).</p> <p> International: Active (statements, leadership).</p>	<p> Securitisation, humanitarian crisis, resistance, legitimacy, terror threat, ethics of war.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war/ conflict, humanitarian, resistance/retaliation.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war/ conflict, humanitarian, resistance/retaliation.</p>
2	<p> Hamas: “Guerrilla movement”, “rulers of Gaza”, initiators of “largest ever military blow”; strategic actors but responsible for “deadly raid”, “hostages”, “civilian casualties”.</p> <p> Israel: Victim of surprise attack; state under siege; agent of “indiscriminate bombing” and “possible re-occupation”.</p> <p> Civilians: Overwhelming majority victims; passive.</p> <p> International actors: Israeli right-wing (calls for “cruel retaliation”), PA (fading influence).</p>	<p> Guerrilla movement, military blow, deadly raid, hostages, siege, expulsion, retaliation, ethnic cleansing, occupation, open air prison.</p>	<p> Hamas: Active (decides escalation, keeps initiative).</p> <p> Israel: Passive (helpless victim) and active (bombing, military rule).</p> <p> Civilians: Passive (casualties).</p> <p> International: Active (calls for escalation)</p>	<p> Securitisation, leadership struggle, humanitarian crisis, negotiation.</p>	<p> Securitisation, historical analogy, resistance, negotiation, necropolitics.</p>	<p> “Devastating assault”, “overwhelming majority civilians”, “gunned down in their homes”, “cruel retaliation”, “open air prison”.</p>
3	<p> Hamas / Palestinian militants: “Gunmen”, “terrorists”, “militants”; initiators of violence, planners of attack, responsible for shootings and abductions.</p> <p> Israel: Civilians as innocent victims (festivalgoers, young people “partying at dawn”).</p> <p> Civilians: Israeli victims, quoted in first person; relatives searching for loved ones.</p> <p> International actors: Israeli rescue services, authorities.</p>	<p> Militants, terrorists, gunfire, abductions, hostages, code red, death toll, burnt out cars, bodies on the ground.</p>	<p> Hamas: Active (planners, aggressors).</p> <p> Israel: Passive (victims).</p> <p> Civilians: Passive (victims, eyewitnesses).</p> <p> International: Active (rescue, official statements).</p>	<p> Terrorism, humanitarian crisis, chaos, trauma, abduction.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war on terror, victimhood, trauma</p>	<p> “Spraying people”, “masses of wounded”, “terrible”, “dying all around”, “chaos”, “nobody is helping us”.</p>
4	<p> Netanyahu: Principal architect of failure, “liability”, “responsible for catastrophe”, “vengeful”, “confrontational”.</p> <p> Hamas: “Murderous”, “inhuman”, perpetrators of “atrocious onslaught”.</p> <p> Israel civilians: Victims.</p> <p> International community: Neglectful, called to act.</p>	<p> Liability, vengeful response, sea of tears, murderous, inhuman, catastrophe, relentless expansion, illegal settlements, siege, occupation, blockade, hostages, crisis, ceasefire.</p>	<p> Netanyahu: Active (escalation), blamed.</p> <p> Hamas: Active (violence).</p> <p> Civilians: Passive (victims).</p> <p> International: Active (urged to intervene).</p>	<p> Leadership crisis, responsibility, securitisation, humanitarian crisis, ceasefire.</p>	<p> Securitisation, legitimacy, ethics of war, negotiation, blame assignment.</p>	<p> “He created a sea of tears”, “failed miserably”, “unprecedented number of civilian dead”, “no justification whatsoever”.</p>
5	<p> Israel: Active military responder, imposing siege, striking Hamas, seeking to</p>	<p> Siege, militants, airstrikes, hostages,</p>	<p> Israel: Active (airstrikes, siege, mobilising).</p>	<p> Securitisation, escalation, humanitarian</p>	<p> Securitisation, humanitarian, war,</p>	<p> “Just getting started”, “will reverberate for</p>

	<p>“change the Middle East”; Netanyahu as decisive leader. Hamas: Aggressor, “militants”, “commanders”, planners of incursion, threatening long war, using hostages as bargaining chips. Civilians: Palestinian victims, “internally displaced”, facing humanitarian crisis. International actors: UN, US, WHO condemning and providing aid.</p>	<p>blockade, displaced, healthcare crisis, evacuation, war of annihilation, paper tiger.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (attack, threats, hostage-taking). Civilians: Passive (suffering, quoted for needs). International: Active (statements, aid).</p>	<p>crisis, victimhood, legitimacy, resistance, international law, necropolitics.</p>	<p>international diplomacy, necropolitics.</p>	<p>generations”, “sea of tears”, “dire situation”, “innocent civilians”.</p>
6	<p>Israel: Military aggressor (airstrikes, siege, shelling). Hamas: Inciting cause (incursion), minimal direct voice. Civilians: Palestinian victims, displaced, suffering “collective punishment”. International actors: Humanitarian/UN/aid workers quoted extensively, focus on crisis.</p>	<p>Airstrikes, shelling, full siege, collective punishment, intensive bombardment, catastrophe, displaced, healthcare collapse, no safe place, blockade, lack of supplies, civilian infrastructure.</p>	<p>Israel: Active (strikes, siege). Hamas: Active (incursion). Civilians: Passive (victims). International: Active (urging protection, documenting crisis).</p>	<p>Humanitarian crisis, collective punishment, international law, securitisation, civilian victimhood, health system collapse.</p>	<p>Humanitarian, war ethics, necropolitics.</p>	<p>“No safe place”, “sea of tears”, “entire families have been killed”, “catastrophe for the entire Gaza population”, “unprecedented escalation”.</p>
7	<p>Hamas: “Gunmen”, “militants”, “attackers”, “rampaging fighters”, responsible for massacre, mutilation, atrocities, described as “aggressive, like animals”. Israel civilians: Victims — “families”, “babies”, “mothers, fathers” killed. IDF/security: Unprepared, responders, rescuers. International actors: Journalists, US President Biden, humanitarian workers (minimal).</p>	<p>Gunmen, militants, massacre, atrocities, mutilated, victims, safe rooms, burned, aggressive, blockade, breached, booby-trapped.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (violent perpetrators). Israel: Passive (victims), active (response). Civilians: Passive (victims). International: Passive (observers).</p>	<p>Massacre, civilian victimhood, barbarity, trauma, war crimes, escalation.</p>	<p>Securitisation, war ethics, trauma, war on terror.</p>	<p>“Killed in their beds”, “cut some of their heads”, “aggressive, like animals”, “smell of death”, “wreckage”, “atrocities”.</p>
8	<p>Hamas: “Gunmen”, “military arm”, deliberately killed civilians, perpetrators of “atrocities”. Israel: “Blindsided”, retaliated ferociously, collective punishment, wholesale retaliation, siege. Civilians: Gazans trapped, precarious lives; non-combatants. International actors: References to international law/humanitarian norms as authority.</p>	<p>Atrocity, collective punishment, indiscriminate, blockade, complete siege, just war theory, occupation, resistance, proportionate, retaliation.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (atrocities). Israel: Active (military retaliation, siege). Civilians: Passive (victims). International: Active (ethical/legal authority).</p>	<p>Ethics of war, humanitarian crisis, international law, collective punishment, legitimacy.</p>	<p>Human rights, war ethics, polarisation, necropolitics.</p>	<p>“Indefensible”, “deliberately killed”, “no justification”, “collective punishment”, “hatred generated”.</p>
9	<p>Hamas: “Attackers”, “fighters”, “gunmen”, “shock troops”, “terrorists”, perpetrators of “massacre”; used paragliders. Israel: Initially unprepared, later retaliated/mobilised. Civilians: Victims — partygoers, families, children, hostages. International actors: Survivors, humanitarian sources, Biden (US support).</p>	<p>Massacre, incursion, paragliders, hostages, barricade, gunfire, siege, vengeance, atrocities, intelligence failure.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (strategic, initiators). Israel: Passive (victims/unprepared), active (retaliation). Civilians: Passive (victims, quoted). International: Active (condemnation, support).</p>	<p>Securitisation, massacre, intelligence failure, escalation, victimhood, trauma, war on terror.</p>	<p>Securitisation, war on terror, trauma, escalation, international law.</p>	<p>“Murder on their minds”, “deadliest day”, “nightmare”, “war zone”, “unprecedented price”.</p>
10	<p>Hamas: “Gunmen”, “fighters”, “militants”, “special forces (Nukhba)”, “terrorist organisation”;</p>	<p>Massacre, terrorist attack, siege, hostages, bombardment,</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (strategic initiators, violence).</p>	<p>Securitisation, massacre, humanitarian crisis,</p>	<p>Securitisation, war on terror, humanitarian, trauma,</p>	<p>“Deadliest day since the Holocaust”, “complete</p>

	planners of audacious attack, perpetrators of massacre, atrocities, hostage-taking; brutal repressors of dissent. Israel: Victims (families, children, revellers), later military responders (siege, mobilisation). Civilians: Both Israeli and Palestinian — victims, displaced, trapped. International actors: US, UK, Iran, Egypt, Qatar, Turkey, aid agencies — mediators, supporters, warners.	intelligence failure, collective punishment, humanitarian catastrophe, war crimes, exile, Nakba.	Israel: Passive (victims/unprepared), active (retaliation, siege). Civilians: Passive (victims). International: Active (mediation, support, warnings).	retaliation, intelligence failure, escalation, hostages, legitimacy, regional spillover.	international law, necropolitics, regional geopolitics.	siege”, “no place of safety”, “hell on earth”, “horrific bloodshed”.
11	UN: Collective moral actor, seeking truce, protection, release of hostages, and aid access. Israel / US: Isolated, voting against resolution, accused of blocking humanitarian relief and undermining international law. Hamas: Perpetrator of 7 October attacks, holding hostages, condemned indirectly. Civilians: Palestinian victims at risk of forced transfer, in need of aid/protection.	Humanitarian truce, ceasefire, aid access, collective punishment, forced transfer, isolation, international law, siege, illegally held captive.	UN: Active (passes resolution, calls for truce/aid). Israel / US: Active (oppose, justify military ops). Hamas: Active (holding hostages). Civilians: Passive (victims).	Humanitarian crisis, international law, legitimacy, ceasefire, diplomatic isolation.	Humanitarian, legal, political contestation, securitisation.	“Enough is enough. This war has to stop”, “day that will go down as infamy”, “untenable situation”, “no respect for rule of law or human life”.
12	Hamas: “Barbaric acts of terrorism”, “atrocities”; catalyst for escalation. Israel: Military responder; target of protest/criticism. Diasporic Jews/Muslims in UK: Victims of hate crimes, intimidation, protest. UK authorities: Politicians, police, religious/community leaders - some accused of inflaming tensions.	Antisemitism, Islamophobia, hate attacks, pro-Hamas protesters, atrocities, terrorist, divisive, multi-ethnic democracy, structural discrimination, fear.	Hamas: Active (instigates violence). Israel: Active (military response), passive (target of protest). Diasporic communities: Passive (victims), active (via community statements). UK authorities: Active (monitor, respond).	Hate crime, polarisation, protest, securitisation, identity, social cohesion.	Identity politics, minority rights, securitisation.	“Appalling consequences”, “shame us all”, “frightening climate”, “utterly inexcusable”, “intimidating time”.
13	Israel: Imposes blackout, intensifies bombardment, initiates siege; accused of war crimes (UN). Gazans: Victims — trapped, displaced, children in orphanages, ambulance drivers. Hamas: Ongoing resistance, secondary role in article. International actors: UN/humanitarian agencies condemning, coordinating aid.	Blackout, siege, bombardment, war crime, trapped, displacement, no safe place, aid trucks, breakdown, contaminated water.	Israel: Active (blackout, bombardment). Hamas: Active (resistance). Civilians: Passive (victims), occasionally active (help each other). International: Active (condemn, aid).	Humanitarian crisis, siege, civilian victimhood, trauma, necropolitics.	Human rights, necropolitics, trauma, war ethics, international law.	“Worst nights of bombing”, “like we were blind”, “doomsday”, “seen too much death”, “no room at UN shelters”.
14	Israel: Accused of collective punishment, forced displacement, violations of humanitarian law. Gazans: Victims — dehumanised, trapped, abandoned. Hamas: Perpetrator of 7 October atrocities. International actors: UN officials demanding ceasefire/aid; US, Russia, UAE in diplomatic debate.	Dehumanised, collective punishment, forced displacement, ceasefire, war crime, atrocities, dangerous evacuation, protected by international law.	Israel: Active (siege/displacement). Hamas: Active (attack). Civilians: Passive (victims). International: Active (advocacy, proposals).	Humanitarian crisis, dehumanisation, collective punishment, legitimacy, ceasefire.	Human rights, humanitarian law, securitisation, necropolitics.	“Matter of life and death”, “abandoned”, “cruel and reckless”, “glimmer of hope”, “no place was safe in Gaza”.

15	<p>Israel: Initiates airstrikes, justifies as targeting Hamas commanders; claims to minimise civilian casualties. Hamas: Victims (in official figures) but also “psychopathic leadership”, “sadistic murderers”, 7 October perpetrators. Palestinian civilians: Victims in “atrocious” conditions, displaced, trapped. International actors: UN/aid agencies warning of catastrophe, using legal language.</p>	<p>Massacre, heinous, commander, graveyard for children, collective punishment, atrocious, siege, displacement, genocide.</p>	<p>Israel: Active (strikes, justification). Hamas: Active/passive (casualties, vows resistance). Civilians: Passive (victims). International: Active (warn, aid).</p>	<p>Humanitarian crisis, legitimacy, securitisation, war crimes, siege.</p>	<p>Human rights, war ethics, international law, necropolitics.</p>	<p>“Heinous massacre”, “graveyard for children”, “living hell”, “psychopathic leadership”, “textbook case of genocide”.</p>
16	<p>Hamas: Perpetrators of “terrorist attacks”, hostage-takers, blamed for civilian massacre. Israel: Victims (1,400 killed, 240 hostages), bereaved families, “frontline soldiers”; government criticised for failures. Families: Active in mourning, activism, peace/hostage release advocacy. Public: Supportive of army, divided on government policy.</p>	<p>Grieving, terrorist attacks, hostages, bereaved, frontline soldiers, massacre, revenge, solidarity, division, community, hope, despair.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (attack, hostage-taking). Israel: Passive (victims), active (policy, war conduct). Families: Active (memorials, protests). Public: Active/passive (support or dissent).</p>	<p>Grief and mourning, national unity/division, victimhood, trauma, legitimacy, militarisation.</p>	<p>Trauma, collective memory, securitisation, legitimacy, resistance.</p>	<p>“We are all grieving”, “moment of silence”, “despair, in horror”, “solidarity”, “no safe place”.</p>
17	<p>ICC: Legal authority investigating Israel for possible war crimes. Israel: Subject of investigation, “friend and ally” of the UK, accused of violations, obligated under international law. UK Government (Tories): Reject ICC jurisdiction, claim partiality. Labour Party: Supports legal process. US: Rejects ICC jurisdiction. Palestinians: Victims lacking sovereignty.</p>	<p>Jurisdiction, sovereignty, war crimes, international law, Geneva Conventions, humanitarian law, collective punishment, two-state solution.</p>	<p>ICC: Active (claims jurisdiction, investigates). Israel: Active/passive (subject, accused). Tories/US: Active (oppose ICC). Labour: Active (supports ICC). Palestinians: Passive (victims).</p>	<p>International law, legitimacy, sovereignty, securitisation, humanitarian crisis, war crimes.</p>	<p>Legal, diplomatic, securitisation, human rights.</p>	<p>“Partial and prejudicial attack”, “matter of life and death”, “far too many Palestinian civilians and children have been killed”.</p>
18	<p>Hamas: Perpetrators of abduction, negotiators in hostage deals. Hostages/families: Victims — children, elderly, mothers; anxious, fearful, waiting. Israeli government: Facilitates deals, criticised for lack of transparency. International actors: Minor role.</p>	<p>Hostages, release, deal, ceasefire, nightmare, Russian roulette, suffering, optimism, fear, trauma, negotiation.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (holding hostages, negotiating). Families: Passive (waiting), active (speaking out). Israel: Active (negotiates), passive (criticised). International: Passive.</p>	<p>Hostage crisis, trauma, humanitarian impact, negotiation, uncertainty.</p>	<p>Human rights, victimhood, trauma, family, legitimacy.</p>	<p>“Living in a nightmare”, “agonising wait”, “like Russian roulette”, “we don’t know”, “survive emotionally”.</p>
19	<p>US: Veto-holder, weapons supplier, diplomatic shield for Israel, accused of complicity in war crimes. Israel: Aggressor (per HRW/UN/NGO) and defender (per officials); recipient of US support. Hamas: Referenced as militant actor; source of disputed civilian casualties. Palestinians: Victims of war; NGOs as humanitarian voices.</p>	<p>War crimes, atrocities, ceasefire, complicity, occupation, ethnic cleansing, humanitarian crisis, international law, darkest hour.</p>	<p>US: Active (veto, supply weapons). Israel: Active (operations, refusal of plans). Hamas: Active (militant action). Palestinians/NGOs: Passive (victims), active (appeals, testimonies).</p>	<p>War crimes, humanitarian crisis, securitisation, legitimacy, resistance, international law, ethics of war.</p>	<p>Human rights, humanitarian, international law, security, resistance, war ethics.</p>	<p>“Darkest hour”, “atrocities”, “catastrophic”, “unethical and inhumane”, “hanging on by our fingertips”.</p>

20	South Africa: Plaintiff at ICJ, defender of Palestinian rights, invokes Genocide Convention. Israel: Accused of genocide, frames claim as “blood libel”, invokes security narrative. Hamas: Referenced as terrorist group, catalyst for conflict. ICJ: Legal authority, adjudicating dispute. Experts/NGOs: Provide legal/political analysis.	Genocide, provisional measures, ceasefire, blood libel, impunity, human animals, irreparable harm, legality, destruction.	South Africa: Active (files case, demands action). Israel: Active (rejects, reframes). Hamas: Passive (referenced). ICJ: Active (adjudicates). Experts: Active (interpret, analyse).	Genocide, legality, legitimacy, securitisation, narrative contest.	International law, securitisation, necropolitics, framing.	“Genocidal in character”, “severe and irreparable harm”, “despicable and contemptuous exploitation”, “You wanted hell, you will get hell”.
21	South Africa: Plaintiff at ICJ, challenger of Israeli actions, catalyst for legal precedent. Israel: Accused of “genocide in manifest violation”, rebuffs charges as “baseless”. US: Israel’s main backer, historically cautious on Genocide Convention. ICJ: Adjudicator, global authority. NGOs/Experts: Provide context and interpretation.	Genocide, blanket bombing, provisional measures, ceasefire, impunity, legal precedent, humanitarian law, intent, state responsibility.	South Africa: Active (brings case, challenges impunity). Israel: Active (rebuffs charges), passive (faces reputational risk). US: Passive (historical position). ICJ: Active (adjudicates, sets precedent). NGOs/Experts: Active (interpret, analyse).	Genocide, international justice, legitimacy, legal contest.	International law, securitisation, necropolitics, historical justice.	“Committing genocide in manifest violation”, “enormous reputational harm”, “crime without a name”, “climate of impunity”.
22	Tal Mitnick: Pacifist refusenik, morally resolute, opposes militarisation. IDF/Israeli state: Enforces conscription, upholds militarism, accused of “apartheid”. Israeli society: Largely supportive of war, stigmatises refusers. Hamas: Briefly referenced as trigger for 7 October. Anti-war groups: Minor but supportive.	Conscientious objector, pacifist, militarisation, occupation, massacre, peace, fear, anti-war, prison, activism.	Mitnick: Active (refuses, protests, advocates). IDF: Active (sentences, enforces). Society: Active/passive (pressures, ostracises). Hamas: Passive (referenced).	Conscientious objection, ethics of war, militarisation, societal norms.	Human rights, anti-militarism, resistance, personal narrative.	“More killing won’t bring back lost lives”, “system is built on oppression”, “I chose not to be complicit”.
23	South Africa: Proactive plaintiff at ICJ, seeking humanitarian protection. Israel: Defendant, dismisses claim as “blood libel”, asserts self-defence after 7 October. ICJ: Supreme legal authority, may order interim ceasefire. Other states/UN: Potential actors for enforcement.	Genocide, blood libel, interim ruling, ceasefire, humanitarian aid, defence, expulsion, threat, provisional measures.	South Africa: Active (files suit, attends ruling). Israel: Active (defends, dismisses). ICJ: Active (delivers, judges). Other states: Passive/reactive (to ruling).	Genocide, humanitarian crisis, international law, legitimacy, security.	Legal, securitisation, humanitarian, framing.	“Highly anticipated verdict”, “threat of genocide”, “self-defence”.
24	Israel / Netanyahu: Assertive, aiming for “total victory”; frames escalation as necessary to defeat Hamas. Palestinian civilians: Victims of mass displacement, deprived of aid, sheltering in Rafah. Hamas: Targeted enemy, initiator of 7 October, holding hostages. US/Egypt/Qatar/International actors: Negotiators, pressuring for ceasefire and aid. Israeli protesters: Demand hostage deal and elections.	Death toll, ceasefire, hostages, humanitarian aid, famine, shelter, bombardment, victory, negotiation, displacement, tunnel network.	Israel: Active (plans, defends, negotiates). Palestinians: Passive (victims). Hamas: Active (hostage-holding, fighting). International: Active (negotiate, warn). Protesters: Active (demand change).	Humanitarian crisis, securitisation, legitimacy, resistance, war ethics, impunity.	Humanitarian, legal, security, war, resistance, negotiation.	“Grim milestone”, “total victory”, “pockets of famine”, “intense attacks”, “unable to move because of bombardment”.
25	Israel: Powerful military actor, accused of collective	Starvation, war crimes, collective	Israel: Active (orders, justifies,	Humanitarian crisis, war	Humanitarian, legal, security,	“Starvation”, “risky

	punishment and “domicide”; frames actions as self-defence. Palestinian civilians: Victims of starvation, displacement, bombardment. Hamas: Perpetrator of 7 October attacks, accused of war crimes. International community/UK/UN: Observers, critics, legal authorities.	punishment, self-defence, domicile, humanitarian law, famine, disproportionate force, incitement to genocide.	controls aid, conducts strikes). Palestinians: Passive (suffer, starve). Hamas: Active (attack, hold hostages). International: Active (warn, accuse).	crimes, legality, collective punishment, domicile.	ethics, framing.	committing war crimes”, “incitement to genocide”, “mass destruction”.
THE SUN						
1	Hamas: Perpetrators of “bloodbath”, “slaughtering” civilians; framed as terrorists. Israel: Victims — “innocent Israelis”, “civilians”. Celtic fans / Green Brigade: Protesters, some portrayed as “brainwashed”, “biased”, “supporters of a terrorist organisation”. Critics (Nir Bitton, ex-players, fans): Outraged, shaming protesters. Supporters: Minor voices in favour of protest.	Terrorists, bloodbath, pro-Palestinian, resistance, traitors, anti-fascist, illicit banners, shame, victory, protest, war.	Hamas: Active (attack). Israel: Passive (victims). Celtic fans: Active (unfurl banners, protest). Critics: Active (condemn, shame). Supporters: Passive/active (thank, support).	Securitisation, terrorism, resistance, legitimacy.	Security, media outrage, protest, ethics.	“Slaughter”, “bloodbath”, “shame on you”, “brainwashed and biased”, “embarrassing themselves”, “victory to the resistance”.
2	Hamas: “Terrorist organisation”, “thugs”, “fanatics”, “killers”; initiators of violence. Israel / Netanyahu: “Defending”, “vengeance”, “blitzing”, “striking back”; authoritative voice. Others: UK/US leaders supportive but largely passive. Civilians: Mostly passive - victims or hostages.	Terrorists, bloodbath, murderers, hostages, “Israel’s 9/11”, revenge, mighty vengeance, blitz, rubble, war.	Israel / Netanyahu: Active (vows, blitzes, warns, promises vengeance). Hamas: Active (launch, attack) — framed negatively. Civilians: Passive (victims/hostages). Others: Passive.	Securitisation, War on Terror, revenge/retaliation, humanitarian crisis.	Securitisation, War on Terror, ethics of war, humanitarian impact.	“Mighty vengeance”, “opened the gates of hell”, “pay an unprecedented price”, “cold-blooded murder”, “terrorists”, “thugs”, “fanatics”.
3	Hamas: “Gunmen”, “terror group”, “militants”, “attackers”; responsible for “massacre”, “killing”, “kidnapping”. Israel / Israeli victims: “Victims”, “attendees”, “hostages”, “missing”; British/Western nationals highlighted. Families: Passive, grieving, searching for relatives.	Terrorists, massacre, gunmen, killed, kidnapped, missing, horror, “music festival massacre”, hostages, bloodbath.	Hamas: Active (kill, storm, parade). Victims: Passive (missing, kidnapped). Families: Passive (grieving), quoted for emotional effect.	Securitisation, humanitarian crisis, victimhood, spectacle.	Securitisation, War on Terror, human rights.	“Chilling last message”, “horrific attack”, “begging for her life”, “terror group’s hail of bullets”, “heart wrenching”
4	Hamas: “Terrorists”, “stormed”, “bloody massacre”. Hezbollah / PIJ: “Terror group”, “militants”, claimed responsibility. Israel: IDF “massing”, “executing”, “defending”, “ready to prevail”; Israeli victims humanised. Civilians: Passive — “told to shelter”, “families waiting”.	Terrorists, massacre, attack, war, “second front”, “emergency government”, “reservists”, “ground invasion”, “Nest of Terror”.	Israel / IDF / Netanyahu: Active (plan, execute, defend). Hamas / Hezbollah: Active (attack) - framed negatively. Civilians: Passive (victims).	Securitisation, War on Terror, military readiness, humanitarian crisis.	Securitisation, War on Terror, military, humanitarian.	“Stormed across the border”, “babies... beheaded”, “ready to execute”, “Nest of Terror”, “ground invasion”.
5	Hamas: “Evil commanders”, “terrorists”, “terror masters”, “murderous intentions”; brainwashing children. Palestinian children: “Baby-faced boy soldiers”, “brainwashed”, “child soldiers”.	Evil, terrorists, brainwashed, massacre, attack, military training, child soldiers, “terror masters”, “new Bin Laden”.	Hamas: Active (train, indoctrinate, prepare) — criminalised. Children: Passive (manipulated).	Securitisation, child exploitation, dehumanisation, humanitarian crisis.	Securitisation, War on Terror, war ethics.	“Evil commanders”, “baby-faced terrorists”, “brainwashed children”, “murderous intentions”, “terror

	Israel / IDF: “Defending”, “storm Gaza”, “responding”. Civilians: “Elderly man”, “victims”, “innocent Israelis”.		Israel / IDF: Active (defend, respond). Civilians: Passive (victims).			masters”, “slumps to the ground”.
6	Hamas: “Terrorists”, “cowardly militants”, “warped group”, “snatched captives”, “dug tunnels”; both menacing and cowering. Israel / IDF: “Retaliated”, “trying to reach terrorists”, “defending” - framed as legitimate military force. Civilians: Implicitly present as hostages or endangered, but not central.	Terrorists, militants, warped group, hostages, booby traps, cowardly, massacre, command centres, abducted captives.	Hamas: Active (build tunnels, abduct), also portrayed as hiding. Israel / IDF: Active (retaliate, defend, target terrorists). Civilians: Passive (endangered).	Securitisation, War on Terror, hostage crisis, dehumanisation.	Security, counter-terrorism, implicit humanitarian crisis.	“Cowardly”, “warped”, “snatched”, “carnage”, “perfected the art”, “scurried”, “buried alive”.
7	Hamas: “Killers”, “terrorists”, “butchers”, deceptive, “well dug in”, indifferent to civilian casualties. Israel: “Troops”, “soldiers”, “specialists”, “planners” — operating in “hellish” conditions, victims of attacks. Others: Civilians as “human shields”, “hostages”; Iran as “bankroller” and trainer.	Terrorists, killers, butchers, human shields, hostages, command centres, blitz, bunker-buster, “death warrant”.	Hamas: Active (plan massacre, build tunnels, set traps). Israel: Active (storm Gaza, assault tunnels, military operations). Civilians: Passive (victims/hostages). Iran: Active (support/training).	Securitisation, War on Terror, humanitarian crisis, resistance, barbarity, legitimacy, international law.	Securitisation, War on Terror, human rights, necropolitics (implied).	“Bloodbath battle”, “hellish rat-runs”, “signed their own death warrant”, “nightmarish labyrinth”, “corpses littered the streets”.
8	Hamas: “Terror group”, “militant”, “top commander”, “negotiator”, perpetrators of “slaughter” and “massacre”. Israel: “Military”, “IDF”, “airstrike”, “responded”, “targeting terrorists”. Others: Civilians — “victims”, “families”, “trapped”, “hostages”; world leaders as supporters or responders.	Terror group, commander, assassination blitz, slaughter, massacre, rampage, hostages, safe zones, airstrike, negotiator.	Hamas: Active (attack, kill, negotiate). Israel: Active (strike, target, respond). Civilians: Passive (victims, trapped). International: Active (condemn/support).	Securitisation, War on Terror, humanitarian crisis, assassination, legitimacy.	Securitisation, War on Terror, necropolitics, human rights.	“Assassination blitz”, “devastating rampage”, “horror footage”, “blaze engulfing”, “grounds littered with bodies”.
9	Hamas: “Terrorist group”, perpetrators of “barbaric murder” and “slaughter”. Iran: “Fanatical regime”, state sponsor, trainer, funder. UK politicians: Demand sanctions and bans; Banks: “Accused” of funnelling millions, liable for attacks. Civilians: Passive victims.	Terrorist group, fanatical regime, funnelling millions, barbaric murder, bankroll, murderous attacks, sanctions, ban.	Hamas: Active (attacking, killing). Iran: Active (funding, training). UK politicians: Active (demanding action). Banks: Passive (accused). Civilians: Passive (victims).	Securitisation, War on Terror, terrorism financing, state sponsorship of terror.	Securitisation, political pressure, War on Terror.	“Barbaric murder”, “fanatical regime”, “despicable acts”, “must end our dithering”.
10	Hamas: Violent abductors, “monsters”, “terrorists”, perpetrators of atrocities. Israel: Victim state defending citizens, trusted government. Hostages / Families: Victims, suffering, powerless but pleading. Protesters: Diverse — some sympathetic, some controversial (e.g., calls for “jihad”).	Monsters, terrorists, hostages, victims, jihad, humanitarian crisis, aid.	Hamas: Active (abduction, violence). Israel: Active (retaliation, rescue). Families: Active (pleading, statements), passive (suffering). Protesters: Active (marching, chanting).	Hostage crisis, War on Terror, humanitarian crisis, securitisation, protest.	Securitisation, War on Terror, human rights, protest politics.	“Monsters”, “butchering”, “murdered babies”, “inhuman”, “beyond shocked”.
11	Hamas: “Terror-crazed”, “butchers”, targets for annihilation.	Terrorists, butchers, massacre, hostages, retaliation,	Israel: Active (military operations, vows to act decisively).	Existential threat, right to defend, retaliation, escalation.	Securitisation, War on Terror, international security.	“Do or die”, “cut head off the snake”, “wiped off the face of the earth”, “terror-

	Israel: "Defenders", "commandos", "troops", decisive military actors. Hezbollah: "Terror group backed by Iran". Iran: "Head of the snake", "bile-mongering Ayatollahs". Western leaders: Quoted urging restraint.	annihilate, terror-crazed.	Hamas / Hezbollah: Passive (targets of retaliation), active in past attacks. Iran: Active (threat rhetoric). Western leaders: Passive/active (statements, calls for restraint).			crazed", "butchers".
12	Hamas: "Terrorists", "gunmen", "brutes", perpetrators of atrocities. Israel / civilians: Innocent victims - families, children. Survivors: Quoted directly for emotional effect.	Terrorists, brutes, hostages, human shields, massacre, innocent, slaughtering, kidnapping, ISIS.	Hamas: Active (commit atrocities). Israeli victims: Passive (killed, kidnapped, traumatised). Survivors: Active (testimony).	Terror threat, dehumanisation, war crimes, humanitarian crisis.	Securitisation, War on Terror.	"Unimaginable terror", "sick crimes", "slaughtering families", "nightmare", "grisly compilation".
13	Hamas: "Terrorists", "savages", "militants", killing innocents, holding hostages. Israel: Victims — volunteers, families, "peace activists", also providing humanitarian aid. Others: Charities, volunteers, hostages' families, international actors.	Terrorists, savages, militants, volunteers, hostages, victims, human shields, peace activists.	Hamas: Active (violence, hostage-taking). Israeli volunteers: Passive (victims), sometimes active (aid). International: Active (support, statements).	Humanitarian crisis, terrorism, victimhood, resistance, right to defend, war ethics.	Securitisation, humanitarian, war ethics, human rights.	"Murdered by savages", "unspeakable cruelty", "horror ordeal", "slaughtered", "heartbreak".
14	Hamas: Abductors, hostage-takers; framed only as a threat. Israelis / hostages: Innocent victims and grieving families, humanised with stories and images. Qatar: Mediator/diplomatic actor.	Hostages, abducted, kidnapped, victims, families, negotiation, prayers, embassy.	Families / protesters: Active (pleading, organising). Hostages: Passive (victims). Qatar: Active (mediation role).	Hostage crisis, humanitarian appeal, diplomatic negotiation.	Humanitarian, emotional, securitisation.	"Each second is an eternity for the families", "Imagine it's yours", "plead", "prayed for her cousins".
15	Hamas: "Monsters", "barbarians", "terrorists"; dehumanised as sadistic perpetrators. Israel: Victims, righteous defenders; family voices foregrounded. Others: Victims such as Shani Louk and her family - peace activists, innocent civilians.	Terrorists, monsters, barbarians, victim, peace activist, hostages, massacre, bloodbath, beheaded, mutilated.	Hamas: Active (kidnapping, killing, parading bodies). Israel: Active (military response, victim identification). Families: Passive (victims), active (speaking out).	Right to defend, barbarity, humanitarian crisis, victimhood, legitimacy.	Securitisation, War on Terror, human rights, dehumanisation.	"Unfathomable horror", "slaughterhouse", "sadistic animals", "blood flowing on the streets", "nightmare".
16	Hamas: "Terrorists", "militants", "Islamic Jihad operatives", "warped group", "losing control"; accused of using civilian sites as shields. Israel / IDF: "Soldiers", "fighters" storming strongholds, "vowing to crush Hamas". Others: Civilians, hospital staff (quoted denying IDF claims).	Terrorists, militants, stronghold, command and control, massacre, shield, booby traps, Hamas-run territory, deadly assault, bombardment, innocent civilians.	Israel: Active (storm, reclaim control, bombard). Hamas: Active (use shields, resist), sometimes portrayed as passive (losing control). Civilians: Passive (victims). Hospital staff: Active (statements).	Right to defend, securitisation, War on Terror, humanitarian crisis, legitimacy of military action.	Securitisation, terrorism, humanitarian crisis, legitimacy discourse.	"Bloody ten-hour gunfight", "crucial stronghold", "crush Hamas", "relentless bombardment", "buried by strikes".
17	Hamas: "Terror group", "terrorists", "vowed", "snatched" hostages. Israel / IDF: Military actors - "soldiers", "warned", negotiating, striking. Civilians (Palestinian): "Displaced", "fleeing for their lives".	Terror group, terrorists, hostages, prisoners, civilians, children, human shields, massacre, war zone.	Israel: Active (strikes, negotiations, warnings). Hamas: Active (release hostages, make demands). Civilians: Passive (flee, suffer).	Humanitarian crisis, right to defend, terror threat, legitimacy, mediation.	Ceasefire, Securitisation, humanitarian, mediation, war ethics	"Fleeing for their lives", "brutal crossfire", "flattened", "horrific suffering", "dangerous war zone"

18	<p>Hamas: “Hordes”, “savages”, “murderers”; violent agents without direct quotes.</p> <p>Israel: “Peace activist”, “child trauma expert”, “victims”, “survivors”, “children”, “family”.</p> <p>Others: Palestinians mentioned as mourners.</p>	<p>Terrorists, hostages, survivors, trauma, hope, legacy, massacre, horror, slaughtered, carnage, peace activist.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (violence, murder).</p> <p>Israel: Active (care, survival), passive (victimhood).</p> <p>Families/children: Passive (victims).</p>	<p>Humanitarian crisis, legacy, trauma, hope, resilience, peace, war on civilians.</p>	<p>Humanitarian, victimisation, trauma, memory, peace.</p>	<p>“Slaughtered”, “ruthlessly cut down”, “hell of Gaza”, “miraculously survived”, “message of hope”.</p>
19	<p>Hamas: “Terrorists”, “fighters”, using “twisted” and “heinous” tactics — psychological warfare, booby traps, lures.</p> <p>Israel / IDF: Victims of these tactics but also responsible for tragic errors (e.g., shooting hostages, church deaths).</p> <p>Others: Civilians/hostages as innocent victims; Pope Francis, Biden, UN quoted.</p>	<p>Terror group, terrorists, booby traps, psychological warfare, hostages, civilian casualties, white flag, mistake, calamity.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (deceptive tactics).</p> <p>Israel: Active (operations), passive (accusations, mistakes).</p> <p>Civilians/hostages: Passive (victims).</p>	<p>Securitisation, right to defend, humanitarian crisis, barbarity, psychological warfare, legitimacy, ethics of war.</p>	<p>Securitisation, War on Terror, humanitarian ethics, international law.</p>	<p>“Twisted”, “heinous”, “heart-wrenching mistake”, “calamity”, “chilling footage”.</p>
20	<p>Hamas: Persistent threat, “Gaza’s Bin Laden”, blamed for tunnels and civilian suffering.</p> <p>Israel / IDF: Active defenders, strategists, protecting soldiers, responding to terror.</p> <p>Civilians/Gazans: Displaced, suffering, lacking aid.</p>	<p>Terrorists, Gaza’s Bin Laden, human shields, relentless bombardment, densely populated enclave, hostages, IDF soldiers, civilian areas.</p>	<p>Israel / Netanyahu: Active (vows, visits, speeches).</p> <p>Hamas: Active (refuse ceasefire, fight).</p> <p>Civilians: Passive (victims).</p>	<p>Securitisation, right to defend, humanitarian crisis.</p>	<p>Securitisation, war ethics, human cost, legitimacy.</p>	<p>“We’re not stopping”, “until we finish them”, “relentless bombardment”, “massive displacement”.</p>
21	<p>Israel on high alert for ‘revenge attacks’ as Iran blames them for bombing that killed 100 & Hezbollah vows ‘punishment’</p>	<p>Zionist regime, terrorist group, revenge attacks, punishment, heinous crime, victims, aggressive, severe reaction, resistance.</p>	<p>Iran: Active (blame Israel, vow punishment).</p> <p>Hezbollah: Active (promise retaliation).</p> <p>Israel: Active (military stance), passive (accused).</p> <p>US / UN / France: Passive/active (urge restraint, deny involvement)</p>	<p>Securitisation, War on Terror, legitimacy, retaliation, humanitarian risk, diplomacy.</p>	<p>Securitisation, war rhetoric, regional security, resistance, victimhood.</p>	<p>“High alert”, “ignite resistance”, “devastating consequences”, “vowed to hunt down terrorists”, “severe reaction”.</p>
22	<p>Hamas: Militants, captors, abductors, terrorists.</p> <p>Israel: Victims, survivors, families, “people of Israel”.</p> <p>Hostages: Innocent, helpless, symbolic figures.</p>	<p>Terrorists, militants, hostages, victims, abducted, murdered, pleaded for her life, symbol of the attacks.</p>	<p>Hamas: Active (abduction, release videos).</p> <p>Hostages: Passive (suffering, symbolic).</p> <p>Families: Active (appeals), passive (grieving).</p>	<p>Humanitarian crisis, terrorism, victimhood, hostage diplomacy.</p>	<p>Securitisation, emotional humanitarianism, war reporting.</p>	<p>“Screamed for mercy”, “harrowing clip”, “slaughtered”, “disturbing footage”.</p>
23	<p>Hamas: “Terrorists”, “fighters”, “militia allies”, “chiefs”; use tunnels for attacks.</p> <p>Israel / IDF: “Military”, “special ops”, “elite soldiers”, “disguised as medics”; strategic, technologically advanced, defensive.</p> <p>Others: Hostages, civilians, UN staff, aid providers, media (BBC, AP, Getty).</p>	<p>Terror tunnels, Gaza Metro, underground strongholds, terror base, hostages, civilians, blitz, neutralise, entomb, sponge bombs, booby traps.</p>	<p>Israel / IDF: Active (destroy tunnels, deploy tactics).</p> <p>Hamas: Passive (targeted), active (build/use tunnels).</p> <p>Civilians: Passive (at risk, displaced).</p>	<p>Right to defend, counter-terrorism, humanitarian risk, military innovation, ethics of war.</p>	<p>Securitisation, War on Terror, humanitarian crisis, military ethics.</p>	<p>“Relentlessly pounding”, “hellbent”, “entomb Hamas terrorists”, “trapped civilians”, “gruelling war”.</p>
24	<p>Hamas / Yahya Sinwar: Demonised — “brute”, “Bin Laden”, “terror chief”; depicted as cowardly and criminal.</p> <p>Israel / IDF: Heroic, relentless, technologically advanced, legitimate military actor.</p>	<p>Terror chief, brute, Gaza’s Bin Laden, mastermind, dead man walking, terror monster, extremist group, stormed, legitimate military actor.</p>	<p>Israel / IDF: Active (hunt, vow to catch, rescue).</p> <p>Hamas: Passive (flee, hide), active in past attacks.</p> <p>Hostages: Passive (rescued).</p>	<p>War on Terror, right to defend, heroism, barbarity, criminality.</p>	<p>Securitisation, war ethics, dehumanisation.</p>	<p>“Brute”, “terror monster”, “twisted psyche”, “dead man walking”, “fleeing in terror tunnel”.</p>

	Hostages: Passive but rescued through Israeli action.					
25	<p> Hamas: Captors, negotiators, leaders, officials; aggressors in conflict.</p> <p> Israel: Government, negotiators, military, Netanyahu, "the Occupation", IDF.</p> <p> Others: Hostages, Palestinian prisoners, civilians, protesters, international community (UN, US).</p>	<p> Terrorists, murderers, hostages, criminals, prisoners, victims, refugees, aggression, humanitarian aid.</p>	<p> Israel: Active (negotiate, military action, resist demands).</p> <p> Hamas: Active (negotiate, attack).</p> <p> Hostages / civilians: Passive (victims).</p> <p> International: Active (support).</p>	<p> Hostage exchange, right to defend, humanitarian crisis, resistance, peace process.</p>	<p> Securitisation, humanitarian, war ethics, legitimacy, resistance, international relations.</p>	<p> "Bloodbath", "delusional cost", "endless cycle", "in the name of humanity", "forced to flee".</p>
THE TELEGRAPH						
1	<p> Hamas: Brutal, inhuman "terrorists"; perpetrators of mass violence.</p> <p> Israel: Victims, stunned, grieving; justified in retaliation.</p> <p> Civilians/Hostages: Passive victims.</p> <p> Political leaders: Mostly commentators or supporters.</p>	<p> Terrorists, butcher, gunmen, Islamist group, militants, hostages, victims, innocent civilians, paraded, slaughtered.</p>	<p> Hamas: Active (attackers, initiators of violence).</p> <p> Israel: Reactive/retaliator y (defenders, avengers).</p> <p> Civilians/hostages: Passive.</p> <p> Political leaders: Commentators.</p>	<p> Terrorism, securitisation, right to defend, humanitarian crisis, barbarity, regional escalation.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war on terror, war ethics, humanitarian crisis.</p>	<p> "Butcher", "slaughtered", "stunned", "mighty vengeance", "appalling violence", "massacre", "cold-blooded murder", "astonishment", "unprecedented".</p>
2	<p> Hamas: Terror group; planners of attack.</p> <p> Israel: Powerful military actor, defender.</p> <p> Civilians: Victims, mainly quoted as witnesses.</p>	<p> Terrorists, hostages, militants, civilians, victims, retaliation, siege.</p>	<p> Israel: Active ("pounded", "unleashed").</p> <p> Hamas: Active ("claimed", "warned", "planned").</p> <p> Civilians: Passive.</p>	<p> Securitisation, right to defend, humanitarian crisis, retaliation, barbarity.</p>	<p> Securitisation, humanitarian, war ethics.</p>	<p> "Enormous bombardment", "one of the heaviest ever", "nightmare", "dreadful retaliation", "everything was turned upside down", "punishing siege".</p>
3	<p> Hamas: Terrorists, "savages"; perpetrators of civilian slaughter.</p> <p> Israel/Partygoers: Victims, mourning, seeking safety.</p> <p> Families: Suffering, powerless, searching.</p>	<p> Terrorists, massacre, ambushed, slaughtering, human shields, hostages, victims, missing children.</p>	<p> Hamas: Active (ambushing, killing, kidnapping).</p> <p> Partygoers: Initially passive, then active (escaping).</p> <p> Families: Passive.</p>	<p> Terrorism, humanitarian crisis, victimhood, dehumanisation.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war on terror, human rights.</p>	<p> "Slaughtering anyone in their path", "lost all humanity, like savages", "numb with despair", "killing us", "shooting at us", "paraded through the streets".</p>
4	<p> Hamas: Perpetrators, planners of attack.</p> <p> Israel: Victims; also framed as having intelligence failure.</p>	<p> Terrorists, hostages, insurgents, civilians, soldiers.</p>	<p> Hamas: Active (planning, executing attack).</p> <p> Israeli intelligence: Passive/failed.</p> <p> Army: Responders.</p>	<p> Intelligence failure, security, legitimacy, threat, crisis.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war on terror, war ethics.</p>	<p> "Biggest security failure in 50 years", "massacred", "bitter taste of the debacle", "recklessness has brought war".</p>
5	<p> Hamas: Perpetrators of massacre; "terrorists", "animals", "bloodthirsty murderers", "barbaric", compared to ISIS and Nazis.</p> <p> Israel: Victims, survivors, military responders.</p> <p> Others: Civilians, politicians, IDF soldiers, survivors, international actors.</p>	<p> Terrorists, animals, barbarism, pure evil, murderers, massacre, pogroms, civilians, hostages, invaders, bloodthirsty, victims, elderly, babies, partygoers, peace activists.</p>	<p> Hamas: Active (attackers).</p> <p> Israeli military: Active (responders).</p> <p> Civilians: Passive victims.</p>	<p> Massacre, right to defend, terror threat, humanitarian crisis, barbarity, legitimacy, international law, anti-Semitism.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war ethics, humanitarian crisis, atrocity discourse, anti-Semitism.</p>	<p> "Slaughtered babies", "butchered", "pure, unadulterated evil", "in an Isis way", "pogroms", "massacre", "barbarism", "depravity seems to have no limit".</p>

						“bloodthirsty murderers”.
6	<p> Hamas: “Terrorists” using civilians as human shields; calling for protest.</p> <p> Israel: Active military, ordering evacuation, planning ground invasion.</p> <p> Palestinians: Civilians under threat, displaced, suffering casualties.</p> <p> UN: Humanitarian voice warning of dire consequences.</p>	<p> Terrorists, civilians, human shields, ground assault, evacuation, humanitarian consequences, hostages, retaliation.</p>	<p> Israel: Active (“orders”, “amasses tanks”, “pounding Gaza”).</p> <p> Hamas: Active (“urging protest”, “hiding”).</p> <p> Palestinians: Mostly passive.</p> <p> UN: Active as critic.</p>	<p> Humanitarian crisis, right to self-defence, war on terror, legitimacy, displacement.</p>	<p> Securitisation, human rights, war ethics, legitimacy.</p>	<p> “Now is a time for war”, “devastating humanitarian consequences”, “using you as human shields”, “innocent civilians”.</p>
7	<p> Hamas: Secretive, militarised; builders/operators of tunnel “labyrinth”; responsible for endangering civilians and using them as shields.</p> <p> Israel/IDF: High-tech, rational actors responding to security threats, facing urban warfare challenges.</p> <p> Civilians: At risk, used as shields.</p>	<p> Terrorists, Hamas leaders, command-and-control, human shields, booby traps, hostages, civilian residents, underground network, blockade.</p>	<p> Israel/IDF: Active (“targeting”, “clearing”, “destroying”).</p> <p> Hamas: Active (“building”, “preparing”, “hiding”).</p> <p> Civilians: Passive.</p> <p> Experts: Active commentators.</p>	<p> Right to defend, counter-terrorism, urban warfare, humanitarian crisis.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war on terror, legitimacy, ethics of war.</p>	<p> “Labyrinth”, “fraught with danger”, “booby traps”, “unprecedented incursion”, “human shields”, “bombing campaign”, “underground infrastructure longer than the London Underground”.</p>
8	<p> Hamas: “Terrorists”, “militants”, “armed wing”.</p> <p> Israel: “IDF”, “defending”, “retaliating”.</p> <p> Palestinians: “Civilians”, “refugees”, “victims”.</p> <p> Western leaders: Supporters, mediators.</p>	<p> Terrorists, militants, hostages, civilians, refugees, right to defend, war crimes.</p>	<p> Israel: Active military actor.</p> <p> Hamas: Active instigator/threat.</p> <p> Palestinians: Passive sufferers.</p> <p> US/UK/EU: Active mediators.</p>	<p> Humanitarian crisis, right to defend, international law, securitisation.</p>	<p> Securitisation, humanitarianism, war ethics.</p>	<p> “Appalling attacks”, “bone-chilling”, “iron-clad support”, “utterly unrealistic”, “unacceptable levels of civilian casualties”, “hellhole”, “catastrophe”.</p>
9	<p> Hamas: “Commanders”, “terrorists”, perpetrators of “massacres”.</p> <p> Israel: Military actor carrying out “strikes” and “raids”, prioritising “rescue”.</p> <p> Gaza civilians: Victims.</p> <p> US: Deterrent actor.</p>	<p> Commander, elite Nukhba forces, massacres, terrorists, hostages, raid, incursion, victims.</p>	<p> Israel: Active (controlling narrative, taking military action).</p> <p> Hamas: Targeted, blamed.</p> <p> Palestinian civilians: Passive.</p> <p> US: Active deterrence.</p>	<p> Securitisation, war on terror, hostage rescue, humanitarian crisis.</p>	<p> Securitisation, legitimacy, humanitarian.</p>	<p> “Deadly assault”, “eliminate Hamas leadership”, “dead man walking”, “heavy airstrikes”, “hostages”, “elaborate network of tunnels”, “deter regional war”.</p>
10	<p> Israel: Aggressor (“terrorising”).</p> <p> Gaza civilians: Passive victims.</p>	<p> Terror, ground offensive, obliterated, bombardment, morgues are full, waiting to die.</p>	<p> Israel: Active.</p> <p> Gaza civilians: Passive sufferers.</p>	<p> Humanitarian crisis, terror, victimhood, legitimacy.</p>	<p> Securitisation, humanitarian, war ethics.</p>	<p> “Complete despair”, “unimaginable horror”, “every person in Gaza is waiting to die”, “using ice cream trucks for the dead”.</p>
11	<p> Hamas: Depicted as a terrorist organisation with 30–40,000 fighters, targeted militarily and politically, enemy to be “crushed”.</p>	<p> “terrorists”, “Islamist group”, “militants”, “security failure”, “ethnic cleansing”, “occupation”,</p>	<p> Israel: Active (planning, military operations, defensive measures).</p>	<p> Right to defend, Counter-terrorism, Humanitarian crisis,</p>	<p> Securitisation, Ethics of war, Geopolitics, Human rights, International law.</p>	<p> “crush and destroy”, “catastrophe”, “colossal security failure”,</p>

	Israel: Presented as the principal strategic and defensive actor, occasionally criticised for “security failures”. Others: Palestinian Authority, Egypt, Iran, Hezbollah, US; civilians as refugees or victims.	“hard-Right”, “hostages”, “refugees”, “regional escalation”.	Hamas: Active (enemy actor). Others: Reactive/secondary. Civilians: Passive (ordered to evacuate, displaced).	Regional escalation, Displacement, Legitimacy.		“ethnic cleansing”, “nightmarish scenario”, “crime against humanity”, “risk of global conflict”.
12	Hamas: Violent attackers/terrorists. Israel: Defenders. Others: British–Israeli family as innocent victims; UK government as concerned.	“terrorists”, “attackers”, “victims”, “civilians”, “missing”, “killed”.	Hamas: Active aggressors. Israel: Active defenders. Victims: Passive. UK officials: Commentators.	Humanitarian crisis, Securitisation, Terrorism, Victimhood.	Securitisation, Humanitarian crisis, Victim-centred narrative.	“heartbreak”, “devastation”, “blood everywhere”, “pogrom”.
13	Hamas: Terrorist group, accused of misinformation, blamed for misfired rocket. Israel: Portrayed both as alleged perpetrator (by Palestinians) and as defending itself against accusations. Others: Regional leaders, international analysts, civilians.	“terrorists”, “militants”, “innocent people”, “massacre”, “war crimes”, “brutality”, “victims”, “propaganda”.	Hamas: Active (accusing, defending, attacking). Israel: Active (defending, investigating). Others: Reactive (commenting, accusing).	Competing frames (“Israeli airstrike” vs “misfired Palestinian rocket”), blame allocation, Humanitarian tragedy, Propaganda war.	Securitisation, Media framing, Ethics of war.	“massacre”, “unprecedented brutality”, “atrocities”, “God will avenge us”, “unified fury”.
14	Hamas: “Pure evil”, perpetrators of terrorism. Israel: Victim with a “duty” to restore security. Palestinians: Victims of both Hamas and conflict. UK: Supporter and mediator.	“terrorists”, “hostages”, “victims”, “darkest hour”, “humanitarian crisis”, “blockade”.	Israel: Active (defending, restoring security, allowing aid). Hamas: Aggressor. UK: Active mediator/supporter Palestinians: Passive sufferers.	Securitisation, War on terror, Humanitarian crisis, Legitimacy.	Securitisation, War ethics, Human rights, International diplomacy.	“unspeakable, horrific act”, “darkest hour”, “pure evil”, “unbearable agony”.
15	Hamas: Existential terror threat. Israel: Defender. US/UK: Security partners. Palestinians: Civilian victims.	“terrorists”, “jihadists”, “saviours”, “extremists”, “hostages”, “victims”.	Israel/US/UK officials: Active (security measures, support). Hamas: Instigator. Palestinians: Passive victims.	Terror threat, Securitisation, Humanitarian crisis, Legitimacy.	Securitisation, War on terror, Humanitarian concern.	“greatest terror threat”, “dire humanitarian conditions”, “scale of the horror”.
16	Hamas: Militants responsible for civilian deaths, blamed for worsening crisis. Israel: Military actor conducting strikes and operations. Palestinian civilians: Victims of violence and displacement. International actors: Aid organisations warning of catastrophe.	“terrorists”, “militants”, “airstrikes”, “hostages”, “displacement”, “humanitarian aid”.	Israel: Active (launching strikes, securing areas). Hamas: Active (launching attacks, holding hostages). Civilians: Passive victims. Aid agencies: Active (warning, appealing).	Humanitarian crisis, Securitisation, Displacement, Right to defend.	Securitisation, Humanitarian concern, War ethics.	“dire conditions”, “children buried under rubble”, “trapped with no escape”, “brink of collapse”.
17	Hamas: Terrorist threat and strategic target. Israel: Defender and retaliator. Iran/Hezbollah: Potential escalators. Civilians: Hostages or casualties.	“terrorists”, “hostages”, “retaliatory strikes”, “regional escalation”, “existential threat”.	Israel: Active (responding militarily, warning of threats). Hamas: Active (provoking conflict, holding hostages). Iran/Hezbollah: Potentially active. Civilians: Passive victims.	Regional escalation, Securitisation, War on terror, Hostage crisis.	Securitisation, Geopolitics, Counter-terrorism.	“on the brink”, “ticking time bomb”, “fight for survival”, “spiral into chaos”.
18	Hamas: Instigators of violence, accused of atrocities. Israel: Military responder, portrayed as strategic and capable.	“terrorists”, “atrocities”, “militants”, “counter-offensive”, “civilian toll”.	Israel: Active (conducting raids, securing borders). Hamas: Active (attacking, resisting).	Securitisation, Humanitarian crisis, Counter-terrorism, Legitimacy.	Securitisation, Human rights, War ethics.	“unimaginable suffering”, “raining rockets”, “fear gripping the streets”.

	Civilians: Suffering casualties, displacement, fear.		Civilians: Passive sufferers.			“relentless bombardment”
19	Hamas: Terror group using propaganda and violence. Israel: Defensive actor, seeking to restore security. International community: Divided between support and criticism.	“terrorists”, “security”, “propaganda war”, “self-defence”, “blockade”.	Israel: Active (imposing measures, engaging in information war). Hamas: Active (spreading propaganda, attacking). International actors: Active (debating, condemning/supporting).	Information warfare, Securitisation, Humanitarian impact, Legitimacy.	Securitisation, Media framing, Diplomacy.	“battle for truth”, “war of words”, “standing firm”, “human shield of lies”.
20	Hamas: Main instigator, holding hostages, resisting Israeli advance. Israel: Aggressive military force, determined to eliminate threat. Civilians: At risk, trapped in conflict zones.	“terrorists”, “militants”, “hostages”, “ground assault”, “urban warfare”, “civilian casualties”.	Israel: Active (storming, targeting, securing). Hamas: Active (resisting, hiding, using tunnels). Civilians: Passive.	Securitisation, Counter-terrorism, Hostage rescue, Humanitarian crisis.	Securitisation, War ethics, Humanitarian concern.	“desperate fight”, “pounding the city”, “trapped without hope”, “streets turned to battlefields”.
21	Hamas: Used as justification in legal disputes; largely passive in narrative, positioned as background threat. Israel: Active defender, resisting legal accusations. South Africa: Active accuser, challenging Israel in international courts. International voices: Mixed – some supportive, others critical.	“genocide”, “terrorists”, “lawfare”, “propaganda”, “blood libel”.	Israel: Active (defending itself legally and militarily). South Africa: Active (pursuing legal case). Hamas: Passive, invoked rhetorically.	Right to defend, Lawfare, International legitimacy, Delegitimation of accusations.	Securitisation, Rule of law, International order.	“bogus allegation”, “modern blood libel”, “abuse of legal order”, “grotesque claim”.
22	Children: Passive victims of extreme deprivation. Israeli policy: Active cause of humanitarian crisis. Humanitarian agencies: Active responders and advocates. Palestinian mothers: Depicted as caretakers in desperate conditions.	“starvation”, “famine”, “malnutrition”, “hermetic siege”, “aid blackout”.	Israeli authorities: Active (restricting resources). Aid agencies: Active (warning, delivering aid). Civilians: Passive, surviving under duress.	Humanitarian crisis, Necropolitics, Structural violence, Securitisation.	Humanitarian, War ethics, International law.	“turning children into skeletons”, “silent killer”, “catastrophic conditions”, “deadly cycle”.
23	Hamas: Underground threat and instigator. Israel: Active military force, targeting tunnels and rescuing hostages. Civilians: Passive victims. UN / aid officials: Active commentators	“terror group”, “militants”, “tunnels”, “aid”, “ceasefire”.	Israel: Active (conducting operations). Hamas: Active (concealing, resisting). Civilians: Passive. UN/NGOs: Active (criticising, warning).	Securitisation, War on terror, Humanitarian crisis.	Securitisation, Legitimacy, Humanitarianism.	“breaks my heart”, “gut-wrenching”, “trampling on international law”, “spider’s web”.
24	Israel: Gatekeeper controlling aid access. Civilians (esp. children): Passive victims of famine and deprivation. NGOs/UN: Active advocates for humanitarian access.	“malnutrition”, “famine”, “critical situation”, “aid blockade”.	Israel: Active (restricting aid). Aid agencies: Active (demanding access, warning of catastrophe). Civilians: Passive.	Humanitarian crisis, Famine, Ethics of war, Securitisation.	Human rights, Humanitarian, Necropolitics.	“children are dying”, “unprecedented globally”, “explosion in preventable child deaths”, “if we do not die from bombing, we will die from hunger”.
25	Israel: Enforcer of blockade, restricting food and aid. Palestinians (esp. children): Victims of starvation and displacement.	“starvation”, “famine”, “obstruction”, “ground incursion”, “aid blackout”.	Israel: Active (imposing restrictions). Humanitarian agencies: Active	Humanitarian crisis, Securitisation, Collective punishment.	Human rights, War ethics, International law.	“waiting the long wait to death”, “heights of inhumanity”, “Ramadan

	Humanitarian agencies: Struggling to deliver assistance.		(trying to deliver aid). Civilians: Passive sufferers.			memories squeezed into a tent".
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Declaration of Use of AI Tools

In this dissertation, I have used the following AI tools:

- ChatGPT – for language refinement and feedback on clarity of expression.
- Grammarly – for grammar and style checking.

These tools were employed solely to support the writing process. The research design, analysis, arguments, and conclusions presented in this dissertation are entirely my own.